

Supporting learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers to transition to open access book publishing (SPA OPS 4.0 project)

by Lorraine Estelle, Dave Jago, Ruth Jones, Mikael Laakso,
Ronald Snijder, and Alicia Wise

An independent report commissioned by UKRI, in partnership with the Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers (ALPSP), the British Academy, and Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA)

February 2025

CC BY 4.0

informationpower

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	3
INTRODUCTION	7
BACKGROUND.....	7
STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT.....	11
PUBLISHER VIEWS	12
LIBRARY VIEWS	16
VISION OF AN OA BOOK WORLD	19
REVENUE MODELS FOR OA BOOKS	20
SUPPLY CHAIN AND WORKFLOWS TO SCALE UP OA BOOK PUBLISHING.....	23
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	27
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	32
CONFLICTS OF INTEREST STATEMENT	33
APPENDIX 1 – INTERVIEWS AND FOCUS GROUPS.....	34
APPENDIX 2 – PUBLISHER SURVEY RESULTS.....	44
APPENDIX 3 – LIBRARY SURVEY RESULTS	53
APPENDIX 4 – 20 SEPTEMBER 2024 CROSS-STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP	61
APPENDIX 5 – CASE STUDY: WHITE HORSE PRESS	69
APPENDIX 6 – CASE STUDY: UNIVERSITY OF LONDON PRESS.....	71
APPENDIX 7 – CASE STUDY: BERGHAHN BOOKS.....	73
APPENDIX 8 – BACKGROUND STUDY AND REFERENCES	76

Executive Summary

The UKRI Open Access Policy introduced an open access (OA) requirement for longform publications from January 2024. Publication types in scope are monographs, edited collections, and book chapters.

UKRI, in partnership with the Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers (ALPSP), the British Academy, and Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA), commissioned Information Power to develop independent advice and a toolkit that can support learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers to explore a range of potential strategies and business models through which they can transition successfully to OA. These publishers play an important role in the research and scholarly communications ecosystem, and that ecosystem is complicated, so there is no silver bullet solution.

Most, although not all, of the smaller and specialist book publishers we engaged with are supportive of OA in principle. They face challenges with unpredictable and unscalable funding models and an array of practical matters. Many feel overwhelmed, understandably, by the pressure for a great deal of practical change and the expectation of time constraints. They need flexibility and time to experiment with and blend the different funding models that already exist, and access to infrastructure to enable these models to scale up sustainably.

Book publishers cannot transition successfully to OA revenue models without the proactive **support of authors**.

- Many authors are enthusiastic about OA book publishing as it can advance their disciplines, broaden access to research, and promote global scholarship.
- However, authors are also confused by conflicting information and terms and want flexibility to choose how their works are used and shared.
- Some authors remain sceptical about the quality of OA publishing. This is a problem of perception, as there can be good publishers and poor publishers under any revenue model. The good news is that stakeholders perceive that this challenge is perhaps waning.

Book publishers cannot transition to OA revenue models successfully without the proactive **support of library customers**.

- Free to access does not mean free to produce. Ongoing funding to support OA book publication is needed.
- Librarians reported that OA is attractive, as books can be added to their collections at no cost, and fewer than a third helped to fund OA book publishing by authors at their institutions.
- Predictable sources of OA book publishing revenue are essential in order for book publishers to transition to OA.
- There are scalable and sustainable revenue models that can enable a publisher to flip one or more existing titles to OA, or to publish titles, collections, or their entire portfolio OA.
- Deciding upon the correct mix of revenue models can be challenging, as much of the current guidance is confusing and some of it is more geared to born OA publishers or publishers much further along in their transition. Practical guidance is needed.
- Many of the revenue models depend on financial support from libraries.
- Direct interaction with library customers is not something many smaller and specialist book publishers have any experience of, or practical prospect of achieving, because this is not scalable for either librarians or publishers.

Librarians face challenges too in the transition to making OA book publishing the norm. All of the librarians we engaged with were supportive of OA in principle. The key challenges they face are financial and practical. Many aspire to transition to OA *and* expand publishing opportunities for their researchers *within the confines of their existing budgets*. This is extremely aspirational and extremely challenging from a financial perspective. Most are in the early stages of transitioning to prioritize OA book acquisition. There are different workflows for open access and traditional books, which creates extra administrative burdens and is a barrier to transitioning their normal purchasing processes to support OA.

In a nutshell, the OA revenue models that are the most promising for the transition to OA *at the time of writing* are:

- **Consortial funding** models have many positive aspects. Publishers gain visibility, awareness, and ongoing financial support through a distributed network of supporters. Libraries gain the ability to select the publishers and book collections they want to support through a central platform. Authors do not need to provide funding to support OA publication of the book. At the moment, the challenge with these models mainly concerns their limited availability and scope, as well as potentially slower decision-making about titles to be made OA due to governance and decision-making processes outside the direct control of publishers or authors.
- **Book Publishing Charges (BPCs)** can work usefully, especially in the short term, because each published title can be priced to cover its direct and indirect costs. There is a growing body of data on how different publishers are pricing their BPCs¹. This approach works well for funded authors; however, many book authors are unfunded, and many funders, librarians, and publishers are increasingly concerned about the equity of this revenue model.
- **Print sales with online OA** models are widely deployed. Offering this option requires minimal inventory capacity or risk, as print can be provided on demand.
- **Green OA** models are a compromise on many accounts, as the book needs to be sold in traditional ways to cover costs, and the author's unpublished manuscript is made available OA with a reuse licence. The OA version may compete with sales. This can be a functional solution in the short term for enabling compliance with OA mandates while other approaches to funding OA book publishing are tested.
- **Digital format freemium** models are where the publisher provides one digital format OA and sells other digital formats. These models are widely deployed, although attention needs to be paid to ensure the OA version does not undermine sales. Some freemium models, for example, only offer "view" access to an HTML version of the OA book with a restrictive licence, so that it is challenging to download a copy and transfer it to an e-reader (e.g. OpenEdition) or to share it.

The supply chain needs to evolve to enable OA book publishing and funding/purchasing on a large scale. We consistently heard three different use cases, each important but distinct, being conflated: discovery of books by libraries who can make purchases or provide funding to make them OA; discovery of OA books by readers; and discovery of OA books by those tracking compliance with OA mandates. It is the first of these use cases that is most problematic in the supply chain.

¹ OpenAPC has been set up to track expenditure on journal APCs and is used by over 400 contributing institutions around the world. As of May 2024 61 institutions had also contributed BPC data for books. See <https://treemaps.openapc.net/apcdata/bpc/>.

Without evolution here, smaller publishers are likely to require more support from larger publishing partners. This would give them the ability to scale up, but inevitably means that their choices of revenue model will be limited to those acceptable to the larger partners.

Systems need to operate on a large scale if all academic books are to transition to OA, especially with expanded opportunities for OA book publishing by scholars. Key challenges in the supply chain include:

- The transition from print to digital is happening alongside the transition to OA, so print books need to be produced and managed alongside their digital counterparts.
- New open infrastructure operates in parallel to book supply chain infrastructure, and the two need to converge.
- There is an unmet need for infrastructure/services to enable many libraries to contribute small amounts of funding so that specific books or collections of shared interest can be published OA, to discover what books could be commissioned and published OA if only the publisher knew that money was available, or to generally commit their OA financial support to a small or specialist publisher in transition to OA *in advance* of publication.
- Visibility of flipped titles is a challenge. Publishers need to be able to clearly and quickly communicate when they have received funding to retrospectively convert a book or chapter to OA, and libraries need to be able to quickly receive and act on this information.
- All of this requires additional metadata, and work with metadata partners, in order to transition to OA book publishing. Formats and editions need to be differentiated at collection, title, and chapter levels. Employers and funders need to be acknowledged to enable OA payments and reporting. Information about the relevant licence needs to travel through the supply chain, both independently and with the full text.
- Infrastructure and services are needed, and need to be affordable and sustainable for all stakeholders.

Hybrid edited volumes are particularly problematic. This approach can provide flexible options when some contributors to an edited volume need to publish OA and others do not. However, there are many practical impediments to their discoverability:

- Publishers use title management systems, digital distribution systems, and metadata management systems. These typically operate at a single book title level, where each book has a unique ISBN identifier which is used to track sales and usage. Layering in an OA business model at a chapter level is beyond the capabilities of many publishers and their book production systems, and the OA status of individual chapters can therefore be difficult – even impossible – to communicate effectively internally, much less across the book supply chain.
- Librarians are not keen on hybrid books. Incorporating an OA chapter, and not the other paywalled chapters, in their catalogues is potentially confusing to users, and causes users to seek out the rest of the book which the library may not have purchased.
- It is therefore questionable whether there would be a sustainable financial incentive to invest the sums required to enable publishers and supply chain partners to create and communicate high-quality chapter-level metadata.

In order to offer a framework for helping stakeholders to make decisions and prioritize actions and investments, a shared vision is essential. During the project we worked with the full range of stakeholders to craft one. It sets out a clear and compelling future that all stakeholders can aspire to. It also serves as a reference point and provides a benchmark against which progress can be measured.

The vision

Stakeholders will work together to create a world in which OA book publishing is:

- **Rewarding and sustainable for all stakeholders** because making longform publications available represents a significant investment of time and expertise from authors, libraries, and publishers.
- **Affordable and accessible** to diverse researchers, research organizations, funders, and those beyond academia.
- **Enabled** by infrastructure that is fit for purpose and embedded in library, publisher, and supply chain partner workflows.
- **Transparent**, leading to communication, confidence, and trust between authors, funders, libraries, and publishers.

And a world in which OA books are:

- **Quality-assured**, so that scholars can rely on and build on the work of others.
- **Findable and usable**, with researchers' work being more widely read and used, in both digital and print.
- **Reusable** under an open licence, typically a Creative Commons licence (CC licence)
- **Preserved** as part of our shared long-term cultural and intellectual heritage.
- **Impactful**, so that academia and society progress more broadly.

The recommendations in this report support this vision for OA books. We conclude that change is needed from all stakeholders – funders, libraries/consortia, and supply chain partners in addition to publishers – if OA book publishing is to scale up and be successful. We set out recommendations for stakeholders in the Conclusion and Recommendations section.

How to Begin the OA Transition: a guide for smaller and specialist publishers was developed as part of our project and accompanies this report. It provides more detailed advice and guidance for both independent publishers and those who work with larger publishing partners.

Introduction

UKRI, in partnership with the Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers (ALPSP), the British Academy, and Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA), commissioned Information Power to develop independent advice and a toolkit that can support learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers to explore a range of potential strategies and business models through which they can transition successfully to OA.

This report is a synthesis of new primary qualitative and quantitative research and a thorough literature review. Our objective is to explain what needs to happen to aid small and specialist book publishers to successfully and sustainably adopt OA models. These publishers play an important role in the research and scholarly communications ecosystem, and that ecosystem is complicated, so there is no silver bullet solution.

The report is structured in this way:

- We provide some background information, which includes a short explanation of what OA is and facts and figures about how much OA book publishing is done and by whom.
- Then we present the discoveries made through interviews, focus groups, surveys, and workshops. These underpin the fundamental importance of revenue models and the book supply chain.
- A vision statement describes a desirable end state for the transition to OA for academic books. The development of this vision was informed by all types of stakeholders, and can be used to inform their priorities and decisions.
- We present an overview of the revenue models available for OA book publishing.
- We introduce the book supply chain and the ways in which it is not yet optimized for OA book publishing.
- Finally, we conclude with recommendations about what needs to happen to deliver the vision.
- Appendices include:
 - A summary of our engagements with stakeholders through interviews, surveys, and workshops (Appendices 1,2,3, and 4).
 - A set of case studies about different types of smaller book publishers who have implemented open-access monograph publishing initiatives (Appendices 5, 6, and 7).
 - A review of the existing literature concerning OA book publishing in the context of learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers (Appendix 8).

How to Begin the OA Transition: a guide for smaller and specialist publishers was developed as part of our project and accompanies this report. It provides more detailed advice and guidance for both independent publishers and those who work with larger publishing partners.

Background

What is OA?

OA refers to the practice of making scholarly research freely available online, allowing anyone to read, share, and reuse the content without financial barriers. This model shifts traditional publishing dynamics, requiring new revenue models to ensure that research publications are accessible from the moment of publication.

OA applies to a wide range of scholarly outputs, including journal articles, books, and conference papers. The primary benefit of OA is the increased visibility and impact for researchers, their work, and their respective fields. By removing access fees, OA democratizes knowledge, benefiting not only readers but also authors and publishers by broadening the reach and influence of their work.

It is important to note that OA is a goal, not a revenue model. However, it is often mistakenly equated with Book Publishing Charges (BPCs), where fees are paid to make books freely accessible. For books to transition to OA, the financial structures supporting them must also adapt. While BPCs can be efficient and work on a large scale, they are also problematic. Pay-to-publish models pose challenges for unfunded authors and in the humanities and social sciences, where authors often lack direct funding for their research. This approach can also undermine equity and inclusion, and is therefore of significant concern to funders, librarians, and other stakeholders whose support is important for a successful shift to OA publishing. Various other revenue models have been developed or are emerging and are discussed in this report, offering potential solutions for achieving scalable, sustainable OA book publishing across diverse disciplines.

How many OA books are there?

It is surprisingly difficult to determine how many books are published each year, much less how many of these are academic books, books in scope for funder OA policies, or books published or retrospectively converted to OA. Answers to these questions are of fundamental importance to tracking market share and rates of change.

For scholarly journal articles, the definitions of what counts as a journal or an article are mature and there are many free and paid services that curate comprehensive data on global output, often filterable by different OA types. When it comes to books, the definitions are not as well established and none of the available discovery services are complete or comprehensive. The drivers for publishers to get books included in databases are not strong: sales of paywalled books are not largely driven by citations, and although usage of OA books is considered important, it doesn't yet drive acquisitions. Whereas with journals, driving usage and citations is key to the health of the journal, this is less crucial for books. While journals will make a concerted effort to get indexed, and there are well trodden paths to doing so, there is less impetus and fewer obvious mechanisms to get book programmes indexed in the same way.

Different databases approach this problem in different ways. Clearly, the estimates derived from them should be treated with caution. Bibliographic databases can provide a rough guide to the state of play but have limitations (Crotty, 2024) and rely on data which may be flawed. They may use different definitions of OA, for example, and these definitions may evolve over time even within a single database as the market evolves. Retrospective intake of data and retrospective conversion of titles to OA can lead to figures changing over time. There are inevitably deduplication challenges.

The number of OA books is growing, but somewhat unevenly and from a very small base. The most comprehensive study to date involved querying six bibliographic databases, discovering 396,995 unique records of OA books, and concluding that around 30,000–45,000 OA books were published each year between 2017 and 2021 (Laakso 2023). This is a tiny subset of the millions of total books published each year, and a small subset of the academic edited books and monographs published each year.

The Dimensions database reports the total number of edited books and monographs published each year as around 89,000 in 2019 and steady at around 101,000 per annum

from 2020 to 2023. However, this underestimates the numbers because the Dimensions database is more focused on journals than on books and does not include print-only resources. Only titles with DOIs assigned are included. The data suggest there has been a rapid increase in OA book titles published in recent years and listed as Gold OA², starting with a jump in 2019 (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Number of records for OA books in Dimensions (accessed 22/7/24)

The DOAB database (accessed 14/3/24) lists 83,039 records for OA books. 17,551 titles were added in 2022 and 16,116 titles in 2023. This must involve at least some retrospective conversion of books to OA, because looking at the books included in DOAB by publication date, we do not see nearly this number of recently published books (Fig. 2).

² Different approaches to Open Access are described using a set of colours. Gold means the work is published OA as the publishing costs are covered upfront in some way. Green means that the publishing costs are covered through traditional sales, and a manuscript version is made available open access. Bronze means the publisher has made the work freely available, but with no reuse licence.

Figure 2 Number of records for OA books in DOAB (accessed 14/3/24)

Who publishes OA books?

9282 (20%) of the OA books included in DOAB are published by IntechOpen, and a further 7246 (17%) by MDPI. The top 20 publishers are shown in Table 1. Note that some significant publishers (e.g. Elsevier and Wiley) do not share data with DOAB and are missing from the database and Table 1. Comparing with Dimensions, Elsevier has 43,031 titles listed under 'Monograph' or 'Edited book'. Of these, 1379 are listed as OA – all of them Green OA. Wiley has 27,525 titles, of which 2026 are Green, 211 are Bronze, and just 5 are Gold.

Publisher	No. titles	% of total
IntechOpen	9282	20%
MDPI – Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute	7246	16%
Frontiers Media SA	2953	7%
Springer Nature	2772	6%
Taylor & Francis	2539	6%
De Gruyter	1296	3%
RAND Corporation	1197	3%
Brill	941	2%
ANU Press	845	2%
KIT Scientific Publishing	739	2%
Amsterdam University Press	664	1%
University of Michigan Press	496	1%
Open Book Publishers	458	1%
Cornell University Press	428	1%

Publisher	No. titles	% of total
punctum books	414	1%
Bloomsbury Academic	409	1%
Peter Lang International Academic Publishing Group	384	1%
transcript Verlag	353	1%
Johns Hopkins University Press	329	1%
UCL Press	318	1%

Table 1 Largest OA book publishers, according to DOAB. Note that this excludes some significant publishers (e.g. Elsevier and Wiley), which do not share data with DOAB.

A further 32 publishers (22 of them university presses) contributed 100–300 books apiece to DOAB. The numbers of publishers with fewer titles listed are summarized in Table 2. As can be seen, a significant number of publishers have listed just one title with DOAB.

No. Titles	No. Publishers
50-99	37
25-49	42
10-24	74
5-9	87
2-4	108
1	134

Table 2 Summary of the number of other publishers contributing to the DOAB database

As stated above, it is surprisingly difficult to determine how many books are published each year, much less how many of these are academic books, books in scope for funder OA policies, or books published or retrospectively converted to OA. OA books are growing in number from a small base, there is a long tail of OA book publishers, and different types of OA (e.g. Gold, Green, Bronze) are already appearing in this landscape.

Stakeholder Engagement

During this project, we had the privilege of engaging with many stakeholders who generously shared their experiences with OA book publishing.

We conducted interviews with a diverse group of smaller and specialist book publishers to explore the opportunities and challenges of transitioning to OA for academic books. The perspectives we gathered were varied and sometimes contradictory, giving us important insights into stakeholder issues and helping us understand what tools they would find helpful.

We then organized focus groups with stakeholders including small publishers, librarians, intermediaries, and metadata experts.

For the first focus group, invitations were sent by ALPSP and the British Academy to book publishers with little or no experience of publishing OA. Engaging with this group was important for understanding the real and perceived barriers and challenges, and informed areas for deeper consultation through the one-to-one interviews and the survey of OA publishers.

The second focus group consisted of ten librarians from diverse UK institutions in different regions and with different foci on research and teaching. The discussion explored how the libraries funded OA books, how they discovered the availability of OA books, and what could help them to financially support and acquire more OA books.

The third focus group consisted of publishers and metadata experts from a range of perspectives including an aggregator, a discovery service, two metadata creators/providers, and a library hub service that supports MARC cataloguing.

Discussions in the focus groups highlighted areas that required deeper consultation and informed a second round of interviews with publishers.

Finally, we conducted surveys of publishers and librarians to check whether the issues and themes that emerged during the interviews were more broadly shared.

This section of the report contains a summary of key findings from the stakeholder engagement. You can find a fuller report of these activities in Appendices 1–3.

Publisher views

Publisher interviews

We invited a diverse group of smaller and specialist publishers of different types, from an array of disciplines, and with different levels of experience with OA book publishing. Those we interviewed:

- Include independent academic publishers, family-owned businesses, subject associations, university libraries, and one former independent publishing house now owned by an investment firm.
- Publish in fields such as archaeology, anthropology, business, business management, cultural history, economics, environmental studies, English literature, humanities, linguistics, religious studies, social sciences, and theology.
- Are at different stages of adopting OA publishing. Some were fully or predominantly OA, others had only published a few OA titles, and some had not yet ventured into OA publishing.
- Had different relationships with library customers, ranging from those with strong connections to those with little direct contact or experience in this area.

The interviews were carried out in two stages. During the first stage, our focus was on identifying the main opportunities and challenges in transitioning to OA. In the second stage, we delved deeper into these issues and the issues that arose from our literature review, and we asked about the tools and guidance required to support the interviewees transition.

From these interactions we selected three publishers and collaborated with them to create the case studies in Appendices 4–6 of this report. The case studies are from a small independent publisher, a larger independent scholarly publisher, and a university press. The development of these case studies³ involved one-on-one interviews with the publishers. Initial drafts were created based on these discussions, which were then expanded and refined in collaboration with the publishers.

³ In addition to the three case studies included here, Barnes & van Schalkwyk (2022) present a collection of 14 OA book publisher case studies.

The publisher interviews flagged up that:

- Most (not all) support OA in principle because it supports their commitment to advancing their respective disciplines, broadens access to research, and promotes global scholarship.
- Authors are also enthusiastic about these features of OA book publishing; however, they are confused by conflicting information and terms, concerned that quality and prestige are maintained when publishing OA, and want flexibility to choose how their works are used and shared.
- Sustainable revenue models are needed for a sustainable transition to OA publishing. Most publishers use a mix of revenue models. Consortial funding models and BPCs currently work best.
- It is therefore crucial to engage more directly with librarians in order to understand customer needs and requirements and to secure consortial funding support.
- Aligning with different funder and institutional OA policies is a new challenge that publishers must navigate if they are to publish OA books.
- Publishers expressed concern that Green OA policies can conflict with their plans by reducing the effective sales period for a book and therefore have the potential to undermine the sustainability of existing revenue models. Publishers would prefer to collaborate with libraries to make final publications OA through the Gold route.
- Publishers in transition need to manage the dual demands of traditional print and OA publishing and highlighted an array of supply chain and metadata issues that erode transparency. Publishers who supply OA information in their book metadata cannot see how that metadata flows through the supply chain and appears in library-facing services and systems. They are unsure if their metadata has been correctly picked up and they are unable to identify and correct problems.
- We consistently heard three different, yet essential, supply chain use cases conflated: discovery of books by libraries who can provide funding to make them OA; discovery of OA books by readers; and discovery of OA books by those tracking compliance with OA mandates.
- DOAB and OAPEN play an important role in helping smaller publishers ensure that their books are discoverable. Organizations such as BDS and OCLC and many aggregators also play helpful roles. Both enables OA publishers to generate open metadata records including ONIX, MARC, and KBART. Greater visibility and better marketing could help Both to scale up.

Publisher survey

There were 42 respondents to the Publisher survey: 8 learned societies, 14 university presses, 14 independent publishers, and 5 library publishers; one respondent was excluded from the analysis as they did not publish books. Full details of the results are given in Appendix 2.

Most of the publishers self-published, while a few worked partly or wholly with a commercial publisher. 35 publishers produced monographs, and 33 published edited books; 19 published conference proceedings, and 18 textbooks. There was broad coverage across STM and HSS. There was a wide range in the number of titles published, with 11 publishers producing 5 or fewer each year while at the other extreme a few larger ones published hundreds of books. The majority had published one or more OA titles, and about half were fully or mainly OA.

Three quarters of the respondents reported that fit with their mission was a principal driver for a move to OA. Roughly a third indicated that author demand was an important

factor, and a similar proportion said that funder requirements were a driver. Only 20% said that financial pressures were important in this respect.

Publishers were willing to experiment with more than one revenue model. Only 7 respondents used a single revenue model, while 11 had tried two or three different approaches and a further 11 used four or more (one publisher had tried 13 different models). It seems clear that no one approach is currently proving sustainable across the board.

The two most common models adopted were hybrid (print), where the digital version is available OA with a print version for sale (17 publishers), and BPCs (15 publishers). Cross-subsidy models and fundraising for donations and grants also featured. Fixed-time embargoes were used by a few, and a couple of publishers used conditional embargoes (i.e. making titles OA when certain targets were hit). Ten libraries were involved with library-based publishing, and a further five institutions provided subsidy funding for a university press. Eight publishers reported receiving third-party subsidies.

The most used consortial funding model was library crowdfunding, whereby an intermediating platform connects many purchasers with the option to unlock a title. A number of publishers who had not yet explored any consortial funding models (and a couple who had) would be interested in learning more about them.

The most common problem encountered in OA publishing, regardless of the revenue model, was the challenge of securing sufficient funding, and it is clear that there is a lack of infrastructure to support publishers in finding financial support in advance of publication.

Metadata was another significant issue, with publishers commenting that the supply chain is complex and not currently optimized for OA books. The problems of adapting workflows also came up, and it was noted that OA requires both significant admin internally and a significant investment of time spent dealing with authors and libraries.

Almost all publishers had the books on their own websites, but several did little else to make them discoverable and were unaware they needed to do so. Over half used platforms such as Knowledge Unlatched, JSTOR, MUSE, OAPEN, etc., and some used aggregators such as EBSCO or ProQuest. Other methods mentioned included commercial platforms, a discipline-specific aggregator, Jisc Library Hub Discover, national library databases, and social media.

It was agreed that usage data was essential. The majority felt it was important for their own purposes, and a similarly high proportion needed it for their authors. Only a third, however, indicated that they needed the data in order to report to library customers. Despite its importance, the consensus was that getting useful data was difficult, and integration of data derived from multiple platforms was not straightforward. A couple of publishers working with commercial partners commented that their partners were not very helpful about passing on the data they received.

14 publishers reported that they had converted titles retrospectively. In a couple of cases these were decades-old titles that were out of print or already in the public domain. One publisher had made some titles OA as a response to Covid, and one had converted a book on climate change. The key factors involved were identified as funding and author willingness. Metadata creation and distribution was again a problem.

The effect of OA on print sales varied by publisher. 7 publishers reported reduced print sales, with the size of the drop varying from 15–20% to 40–50%. A further 4 publishers felt it had little or no effect. One publisher noted that they had largely discontinued the

'Hybrid (print)' model, as the ongoing decline in print sales means it is no longer sustainable.

Increased usage, author satisfaction, and increased reader engagement were held to be the most important indicators of success for an OA programme. Increased citations were felt to be a useful metric by just over half the respondents. Strengthening the list and financial return were each important outcomes for about a third of publishers. Also mentioned were funder satisfaction, extending global reach, reaching new audiences outside academia, and meeting strategic objectives to support early career researchers.

Several publishers commented on what they would do differently if starting now:

- Adopt an open source platform under their own control rather than the control of a partner.
- Get an approved five-year strategy that includes OA, and buy-in from leaders at the outset.
- Establish in-house IT/technical support.
- Pursue additional outlets (e.g. JSTOR) from the beginning, to raise discoverability.

The following resources would have been found helpful:

- Details of funders and mandates.
- Robust guidance on best practice for developing OA contracts.
- Better metadata creation and distribution practices.
- Better usage collection and normalization.
- Review/comparison of publishing software and hosted services available.
- A toolkit on marketing.

The fact that some of these resources may exist already highlights the fact that it can be hard to find out what help is available or to evaluate its usefulness. In addition, some of the existing resources are aimed at specific publisher types and may not be more generally applicable.

[Publisher views from workshop](#)

Participants explored what information publishers need, and when, in order to decide to publish a title OA. OA book publishers typically use multiple revenue streams, and so the data requirements can be daunting.

Publishers would find it helpful to know that there is OA funding securely in place at any point until the book is published. After this, all the problems with retrospective flipping kick in.

In reality, it would be very helpful for publishers to know if OA funding is available much earlier than the point of publication, particularly for titles that will be in subject collections, as these collections are pre-sold and priced a year in advance. Publishers were particularly sensitive to potential accusations of double-dipping if they sold a book in a collection that was then published OA.

We learned that the following types of information are required:

- BPC Models
 - Gathering the necessary information for a BPC model is often complex. Publishers need to identify the relevant research funder, and often need to

- engage in dialogue with author and/or funder to agree the BPC. The amount can vary depending on the length of the book and any specialized typesetting or formatting.
- Often it is the employer, or an organization other than the research funding body, that will pay the invoice, so it is important to have contact with this organization too.
 - There may be time limits on the funding and these can sometimes be unclear. If a book experiences delays such as a later-than-expected delivery by the author or an extended peer review process, then the publisher may miss funding windows.
 - Publishers require clarity about the licensing requirements and they must ensure the author approves publishing their work OA.
 - Collective funding models
 - Jisc has piloted a 6-month funding window for lists of about 10 titles per publisher. These tend to be whichever are the next 10 titles in the publisher's queue. While libraries would prefer to pledge for specific subjects or titles, it isn't possible to do this at present.
 - Publishers need confirmation that the funding target has been met, and this information does not always align with the book's publication timeline.
 - If funding is incomplete the book might not be published OA, possibly causing it to drop out of the collective funding model and creating a potential compliance problem for the author.
 - Even if funding is secured, the author's approval for OA publication is still necessary.
 - Societies that work with larger publishing partners can encounter additional challenges. The responsibilities of the two parties can be or can become unclear, leading to delays or confusion in decision-making as information is passed between them.

Library views

Library interviews

These flagged up that:

- Librarians face financial and practical challenges to support consortial funding models and OA infrastructure, and when making OA books discoverable to their users.
- Librarians in the UK suggested a Jisc purchasing framework could help streamline the process, reducing the need for individual assessments of book publishers and their policies each time.
- They are not keen on hybrid books where some chapters are OA and others are not. Incorporating an OA chapter, and not the other paywalled chapters, in their catalogues was potentially confusing to users, and caused users to seek out the rest of the book which the library may not have purchased.
- Libraries want books on faculty reading lists to be published OA. They are concerned that much of the content in consortial funding packages is peripheral to their core and strategic requirements. This fuels mistrust and concerns that publishers are more motivated by revenue protection than by OA.
- Librarians want greater clarity on the value of OA offers and would welcome advice about how to demonstrate this value to finance and procurement teams.

Library Survey

There were 185 respondents to the library survey (174 were from libraries and 5 were from consortia, 4 were research organizations, one was a professional library association, and one was an independent retired librarian). The bulk of the responses came from the UK (42%) and the USA (22%). Full details for the results are given in Appendix 3.

We asked respondents to describe their approach to OA academic books. A primary driver was to add books to collections at no cost (70% of respondents). In addition, there was support for OA infrastructure (66%). Clearly, though, ongoing funding to support OA publication of actual titles is needed if books are to continue to be published at all, and only 29% of respondents fund OA book publishing for authors at their institutions.

Respondents listed 59 different initiatives they currently participate in to support OA academic books, which indicates the wide range of options available for libraries to assess and the demand on resources to make those assessments. Given the plethora of options, it is perhaps unsurprising that there was some confusion noted as to both the names and the coverage of some initiatives. There was considerable variation in the number of initiatives supported: many libraries reported supporting about half a dozen initiatives, but the numbers ranged from 1 to 25.

Some respondents expressed limited support for BPCs, but more singled these out as undesirable (and it was noted that the requirement to provide funding well in advance of publication was problematic).

The most popular models were diamond (although there were no suggestions as to how to fund this) and consortial funding models. Transparency was felt to be key. Models which give access to a paywalled backlist as part of the deal were liked, as they allow the library to demonstrate a direct benefit of the funding (although the lack of input into the selection of paywalled titles was problematic). However, there is a tension between the expectation that HEI libraries should answer to local requirements and the broader benefits that flow from the collaborative action needed to fund an OA transition.

Pledge models do not always meet their target and unlock; even when they do, the turnaround time for making titles OA can be sluggish. For institutional authors, selection for OA publication can't be assured when it is dependent on selection or funding criteria, and a lack of guaranteed benefits makes demonstration of return on investment problematic.

Not all libraries felt the need to evaluate a return on investment in OA, and many reported that they had no means of doing so, either because the problem seemed intractable, or because it hadn't yet been required. Return on investment (ROI) evaluations fell into two camps: those undertaken before committing funds (where factors such as cost, relevance of backlist offered, and inclusion of the institution's authors in the backlist were considered), and those carried out after publication, where feedback from faculty, inclusion of material on reading lists, and the number of outputs produced with authors from the institution were among the key criteria.

There was no consistent approach used to learn about individual monographs, and some librarians noted that they didn't really have a system. Publisher mailings were helpful, although only a couple of respondents said that they looked at publisher websites. Locating titles in the first place was felt to be a much larger problem than making books discoverable by users. It was straightforward to include titles (or collections of titles) in the usual systems (Primo, OCLC Collection Manager, etc.) provided that appropriate metadata was available. The problem is that OA-relevant metadata is often lacking.

69% of libraries would usually acquire an ebook or a print version of a title, but not both, although this was not a hard and fast rule: both print and ebooks were often purchased for essential texts on reading lists. Nearly half would not buy print if an OA version were available, and a further 38% said that it would make a print purchase less likely. When print is purchased, 90% of respondents stated that the existence of an OA version would make no difference to the choice of paperback or hardback. 60% would be less likely to buy an enhanced edition if a 'flat' OA version existed.

Most libraries reported that it was hard to discover which chapters are OA in hybrid titles and felt that such books caused more confusion and generated more work than they were worth.

Popular suggestions for resources to support librarians in acquiring and promoting OA books included:

- A glossary of terms.
- A guide to different revenue models for OA books.
- Effective tools to advocate for and promote OA monographs across the institution.
- Case studies and testimonials from authors who have published OA books.
- Practical advice on how to make OA titles and chapters discoverable in library systems.
- Advice on ways of measuring value for money.
- A checklist for how to assess quality and stability of OA platforms.
- A central place to find, browse, and pledge/subscribe to OA books or packages.
- A centralized usage reporting tool allowing libraries to look at overall take-up as well as their own use of titles.

The fact that some of these resources may exist already highlights how hard it can be to find out what help is available or to evaluate its usefulness.

There were a number of common threads when librarians were asked what advice they would offer academic book publishers wishing to transition to OA and seeking library support:

- Invest time in talking to libraries and really understand decision-making processes around purchasing and discovery, library workflows, and metadata needs, etc.
- Make costs transparent.
- Make any offer compelling in terms of content and price.
- Be clear about what works will be made OA, and how/when this will happen.
- Be realistic; most libraries are currently not in a position to financially support a lot of OA book publishing (particularly at smaller institutions).
- Avoid BPC models if possible.
- Good metadata is key.
- Explore Green OA models.
- Get your collections into library management systems.
- Make sure you are included in DOAB.

- Make OA information easy to find on your website.
- Ensure any OA scheme is equitable for all authors and readers.
- Highlight the quality of your publishing processes and give examples of what you have published to help encourage author buy-in.
- Provide support for authors securing third-party copyright clearance.
- Meet WCAG accessibility guidelines.
- Keep a robust electronic preservation plan in place.

Library views from workshop

Participants explored what information libraries need, and when, to decide to provide funding so that a title can be published OA.

Librarians flagged a need to be informed when a relevant book is commissioned for publication. Too often they are not informed at all, even at the point of publication. If they are informed much earlier, they can explore potential opportunities to provide funding, either individually or via collective funding models.

- It is crucial for libraries to know which books will be included in collective funding models before the start of the financial years when budget allocations are made.
- They may have access to funding for BPCs as well, but it can take some time to explore this option.
- Requests for OA funding need to be weighed against other potential uses for the same money. It is therefore essential to have a clear business case (e.g. the sum that is needed, how the book fits with their collection and the needs of their faculty, usage statistics for similar books by the same publisher).

Potential helpful changes would be for libraries to:

- Evaluate how OA books can enable and support their own readers.
- Ask consortia to play a role in pooling library resources to support more collective funding models and to support smaller and specialist book publishers to transition to OA.
- Establish a rolling fund for OA book publishing from their acquisition budget.
- Allocate funding to collective models further in advance of publication so that there is a stable pot of money available for allocation to collections.
- Invest any year-end money in collective funding models for upcoming books.
- Request from intermediaries more transparency and frequent reporting for progress on collective funding offers.
- Use purchasing plans to prioritize print acquisition of books where the digital version is OA, particularly those published by smaller and specialized publishers in transition to OA.
- Create or fund the creation of an open dashboard of what OA book publishing projects currently need financial support.
- Raise awareness amongst their faculty of the OA book publishing schemes your library supports financially.

Vision of an OA Book World

This shared vision was developed in dialogue with the full range of stakeholders throughout the project. It sets out a clear and compelling future that all stakeholders can aspire to. It therefore offers a framework for decision-making, helping stakeholders

prioritize actions and investments in line with the desired future. It also serves as a reference point and provides a benchmark against which progress can be measured.

Stakeholders will work together to create a world in which OA book publishing is:

- **Rewarding and sustainable for all stakeholders**, because making longform publications available represents a significant investment of time and expertise from authors, libraries, and publishers.
- **Affordable and accessible** to diverse researchers, research organizations, funders, and those beyond academia.
- **Enabled** by infrastructure that is fit for purpose and embedded in library, publisher, and supply chain partner workflows.
- **Transparent**, leading to communication, confidence, and trust between authors, funders, libraries, and publishers.

And a world in which OA books are:

- **Quality-assured**, so that scholars can rely on and build on the work of others.
- **Findable and usable**, with researchers' work being more widely read and used, in both digital and print.
- **Reusable** under an open licence, typically a Creative Commons licence (CC licence).
- **Preserved** as part of our shared long-term cultural and intellectual heritage.
- **Impactful**, so that academia and society progress more broadly.

Revenue Models for OA Books

Over the last decade and beyond there has been considerable experimentation with revenue models for OA book publishing. The models are a mix of those that can be applied to individual book titles and those that can be applied at imprint or publisher level. The models can be used either individually or in combination with each other.

There has been significant effort in categorizing these models, and while we very much appreciate these efforts, we are not yet convinced by any of them, including our own (e.g. Ferwerda 2014; Speicher, Armando, Bargheer et al 2018; Penier, Eve & Grady 2020; Wise and Estelle 2020; Mellins-Cohen 2024). Publishers often brand and speak about their models and offerings by using unique terms and suggesting that they offer something completely new (Mellins-Cohen 2024). In short, vocabulary is a real challenge.

We therefore felt it essential to provide a summary. For books, we found the report by Penier, Eve & Grady to be the strongest starting place. Missing from this report, and worthy of addition, are Green OA options and their associated revenue models.

Revenue models for OA Books	
Earned revenue models	Short Description
Advertising	A demand-side model that consists of advertisements, contextual links, and/or product placement within the OA monograph or on the publisher's website.
Book Processing Charge	A demand-side model in which publishers charge the author or his/her employer/funder a fee upon acceptance of the book for publication.
Cross subsidies	A supply-side model, in which funding for OA monographs comes from revenues from the publisher's commercial activities such as service provision, institutional funding, sale of translation rights, or profits from other non-OA publications.
Crowdfunding from individuals	A demand-side model, in which the publisher organizes crowdfunding campaigns pitching monographs online to readers.
Embargoed/delayed OA	A demand-side model, in which a monograph becomes OA only after a delay or embargo period, during which only priced editions are available.
Endowments	A supply-side or third-party model, in which the publisher builds or receives an endowment or subvention (for example as a part of a start-up grant) and uses annual interest to cover its expenses.
Fundraising (donations and grants)	A demand-side model, in which the publisher solicits donations, periodically or continuously, from individuals or foundations.
Digital format freemium	A demand-side model in which the OA edition is in one digital format (e.g. HTML) and the priced edition in other digital formats (e.g. EPUB, PDF, MOBI) that may be easier to use and thus have a higher value for customers.
Print sales with online OA	A demand-side model that uses the dual formats of digital and print, which are priced by 'media preference'. The priced version could be a print edition while the online version is offered as OA.
Third-party licensing	A supply-side business model, in which the publisher licenses some of its OA content to third-party distributors and uses some of the revenue to support the costs of OA publishing (the publisher might make the content available for commercial distribution under a separate licence).
Traditional Sales + Green OA	A model where the author's accepted manuscript is made available through a repository. This can be used in conjunction with an embargo or without one. The publisher can still sell access to the final book, although some sales may be compromised because of the availability of the free draft version.
Embedded institutional support	
Library-based publishing	A supply-side model, in which the press collaborates with the university library, sharing resources to make OA financially feasible.
Subsidy model	A supply-side model, in which a university/faculty/research centre and/or library subsidizes a university press directly or indirectly (financially or through facilities, equipment, or personnel, i.e. in-kind institutional support).

Third-party subsidies	
Grants	A third-party business model, in which an institution (learned society, not-for-profit organization, or foundation) subsidizes OA publications, in whole or part, directly or indirectly (financially or through facilities, equipment, or personnel i.e. in-kind institutional support).
Liberation	A third-party model for books that have already been published/are on backlists. Sponsors (foundations or governments) buy the copyright for books and then make them OA.
Consortial models	
Library crowdfunding	A model in which an intermediating platform connects many purchasers with the option to 'unlock' or 'unlatch' a title.
Membership fees	A supply-side model, in which distinct user groups create a platform for economic exchange that provides each group with the benefits of a large network.
Shared infrastructure	A supply-side model, which entails sharing infrastructure and resources.
Subscribe-to-open	A model where libraries subscribe to have access to content. After subscriptions reach a certain threshold, the content becomes openly available to all readers.

Table 3 Classification of revenue models (adapted and cited from Penier, Eve & Grady 2020). These models can be used alone or in combination.

Every publisher's context will be unique, and so it is difficult to provide general advice. In a nutshell, the models that are the most promising for the transition to OA *right now* are as follows:

- **Consortial funding** models have many positive aspects. Publishers gain visibility, awareness, and ongoing financial support through a distributed network of supporters. Libraries gain the ability to select the publishers and book collections they want to support through a central platform. Authors do not need to provide funding to support OA publication of the book. At the moment, the challenge with them mainly concerns their limited availability and scope, as well as potentially slower decision-making about titles to be made OA due to governance and decision-making processes outside the direct control of publishers or authors.
- **BPCs** can work usefully, especially in the short term, because each published title can be priced to cover its direct and indirect costs. There is a growing body of data on how different publishers are pricing their BPCs⁴. This approach works well for funded authors; however, many book authors are unfunded, and many funders, librarians, and publishers are increasingly concerned about the equity of this revenue model.
- **Print sales with online OA** models are widely deployed. Offering this option requires minimal inventory capacity or risk, as print can be provided on-demand.
- **Green OA** models are a compromise on many accounts, as the book needs to be sold in traditional ways to cover costs, and the author's unpublished manuscript is made available OA with a reuse licence. The OA version may compete with sales.

⁴ OpenAPC has been set up to track expenditure on journal APCs and is used by over 400 contributing institutions around the world. As of May 2024, 61 institutions had also contributed BPC data for books. See <https://treemaps.openapc.net/apcdata/bpc/>.

In the short term, this can be a functional solution for enabling compliance with OA mandates while other approaches to funding OA book publishing are tested.

- **Digital format freemium** models are where the publisher provides one digital format OA and sells other digital formats. These models are widely deployed, although attention needs to be paid to ensure the OA version does not undermine sales. Some freemium models, for example, only offer 'view' access to an HTML version of the OA book with a restrictive licence, so that it is challenging to download a copy and transfer it to an e-reader (e.g. OpenEdition) or share it.

Supply Chain and Workflows to Scale Up OA Book Publishing

It might seem odd that we devote space in this report to infrastructure, but it underpins access to both funding for and the supply of and access to books and metadata. While evolving, the supply chain is currently not optimized for supporting OA books. As evidenced in our focus groups and surveys, this is cited as a key challenge to the OA book transition by both libraries *and* publishers and it is the source of confusion within and between organizations.

These misunderstandings can erode trust. Our focus groups highlighted inconsistencies about how book information is exchanged between publishers and intermediaries, intermediaries and intermediaries, or intermediaries and libraries. It is therefore in the interests of all stakeholders to understand and work together to resolve these challenges.

A basic shared understanding between stakeholders about what the supply chain is, how it operates, and what changes are needed is one fundamental building block. We therefore offer a basic introduction here, and more practical advice for publishers in the guide on *How to Begin the OA Transition: a guide for smaller and specialist publishers*.

The Clarke and Ricci [Open Access Mapping Report](#) provides an excellent overview of the OA supply chain, which we have used as a basis for a simplified mapping in Figure 3, to show the flow of digital book files and metadata to the readers from a publisher:

Figure 3 Simplified supply chain mapping based on Clarke & Ricci 2021

The supply chain for books differs fundamentally from the journal supply chain in some crucial ways:

- The supply chain is **distributed**. By this we mean that copies of the full text of books and their metadata are distributed, as opposed to widespread use of redirection technologies guiding users to a master version, as happens in the journal supply chain. Books are distributed to consumption and discovery partners such as aggregators, book stores, distributors, library platforms, repositories, sales channels, etc. A publisher may also make the books and metadata available on their own websites, but these will not be the primary way they are accessed, very visible, or greatly used.
- **Print remains important for book publishers**, and the digital book supply chain partially overlaps with the print book supply chain. There are a large number of points of communication between these supply chains which vary by region, country, language, discipline, and customer type, often exposing and selling print alongside digital books.
- There are **separate supply chains for different types of customers**. The channels through which books are purchased by individuals overlap with, but are also distinct from, the channels through which books are purchased by libraries.
- There are **many intermediaries between publishers and customers**, and influence comes via international and national standards organizations (e.g. EDItEUR, BIC, BISG, NISO).
- The **data requirements of supply chain partners are complicated and opaque**, sometimes by design to protect an intermediary's business interests, and it is not widely understood how data supplied by the publisher or by another intermediary is transformed and displayed to any group of users or customers.
- **Metadata is the lifeblood of this system** – publishers and libraries often outsource services such as metadata creation and provision to third parties, which can improve standards, but can also lead to confusion about the ownership and control of the metadata.
- When there is any **change to the status of a book title**, metadata needs to be resubmitted. However, these updates are not uniformly made across the supply chain (unlike changes to price or territorial rights). Indeed, we found that several data recipients in the scholarly supply chain do not yet accept any OA-related updates. This means:
 - **OA books are not uniformly discoverable and available across all platforms used by libraries and universities.**
 - **OA titles may be available for sale even when the publisher has correctly updated their data feeds to show it is OA.**

These inconsistencies have been highlighted as a problem by both librarians and publishers.

- **While journals will make a concerted effort to get indexed in discovery services, and there are well-trodden paths to doing so, there is less impetus and fewer obvious mechanisms to get book programmes indexed in the same way.** The drivers for publishers are not strong: sales of paywalled books are not hugely driven by citations, and although usage of OA books is considered important, it doesn't yet drive acquisitions. Whereas with journals, driving usage and citations is key to the health of the journal, this is less crucial for books.
- **A new ecosystem of OA book services has emerged and operates with the established supply chain.** Key elements of this ecosystem include DOAB, which indexes and facilitates discovery of and access to scholarly, peer-reviewed OA books, and the OAPEN Library which hosts, disseminates, and facilitates the preservation of OA books. These have become important services for normalizing and disseminating metadata to a wide array of discovery and indexing services. Their position in the supply chain is described in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 New OA ecosystem services

- Demonstrating value for money is important but challenging for all stakeholders.** The distributed nature of the supply chain means it is difficult to collect dispersed usage data and there is no standardized usage statistic

reporting. This data is crucial for demonstrating the reach of OA books to authors and showing libraries the impact of their financial support, both within their institutions and globally. While the COUNTER standard assists libraries in accessing usage data from various platforms, interpreting and aggregating this data into a comprehensive report would require significant staff time. The OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAeBUDT) is a key initiative to enhance cross-platform usage data exchange and aggregation.

- **Most publishers make OA books available beyond the OA-specific and library-specific supply chains.** For many this is a case of ensuring maximum visibility for all titles regardless of business model, but it can also be an option to generate additional revenues, for example through print. Amazon has been mentioned as both a book discovery portal and a sales channel in addition to the 'Big four' ebook vendors (EBSCO, ProQuest, Project Muse, JSTOR). Problems can arise when the ebook is both OA and available on a paid-for commercial platform for individual use. In theory this should not be a problem, but consumer-facing commercial platforms are not well set up for OA. Instead, they may not accept an OA title or might mask its OA status.
- **The costs of including books in multiple platforms can be challenging for smaller and specialist publishers.** Steps to maximize the discoverability and visibility of OA content can be especially problematic as the costs incurred and time required generate no additional revenue.
- **Library vendors also incur costs to ingest OA titles and make these discoverable in library systems.** Some vendors make a minimal charge for their curation and inclusion, but as the numbers of OA titles rise there is a risk that these vendors will sideline OA titles.
- **Retrospective OA needs to be carefully managed through clear communication** with all outlets and updated ONIX feeds indicating the date a title became OA. Some publishers will issue a new ISBN for the OA version, which can mitigate these issues, as long as it is clear that this is a new version of an already published title, and the commercially available version is removed from sale where appropriate.
- **The hierarchy and relationship between chapters, books, and collections needs careful management.** Ideally, each chapter would have its own metadata and associated DOI to enable the chapters to be discoverable in just the same way that journal articles are.
- **For many publishers, however, chapter-level metadata is too complex to manage without additional systems and resources – either in-house or outsourced – which are difficult or impossible to afford.** Many digital distribution systems have only recently supported chapter-level metadata, and not all do so. Some intermediaries break the book into chapters and apply their own DOIs, but not all do. Further, library systems do not always work well at a chapter level, and the additional complexities of managing the book at both a chapter and title level can be burdensome.
- **Collections are traditionally used by publishers and aggregators to group book titles together as packages for sale, and by librarians to select books to acquire.** Whilst it is possible to include OA titles in a paid-for collection, this is cited by librarians as causing more confusion than benefit. Library infrastructure and workflows do not appear to support consortial funding models for OA books very well. Inclusion of a title in a collection can be transient, so unless careful attention is made to update the collection and associated title metadata and keep track of all collections, there can be confusion. Further complications can arise where chapters within a title are made OA, and that title is included in one or more collections.
- **Support infrastructure for facilitating OA funding transactions between libraries and journal publishers is nascent for books.** These services support library drivers such as affordability and compliance with funder mandates as well as the financial arrangements that will underpin the transition to OA.

- **Publishers in transition to OA also need to understand things that are specific to OA publishing.** Examples include OA licences and rights management or the requirements that authors and their institutions have to report on OA compliance to employers and/or funders.

Conclusion and Recommendations

A transition to OA book publishing may be daunting to those publishers just getting started, but there are viable revenue models, and it is possible to start with minimal risk. Make these changes on a title-by-title basis, and an OA transition will follow naturally.

Change is needed from all stakeholders – funders, libraries/consortia, and supply chain partners in addition to publishers – if OA book publishing is to scale up and be successful. If library collection and materials budgets transition to OA, smaller and specialist publishers can follow.

The recommendations that follow are to help stakeholders work well together and align with the shared vision they articulated during this project.

Stakeholders will work together to create a world in which OA book publishing is:

Rewarding and sustainable for all stakeholders, because making longform publications available represents a significant investment of time and expertise from authors, libraries, and publishers.

All stakeholders should:

- **Recognize that rewards are different for different stakeholders.** For researchers, it may be the acknowledgement and reach of their intellectual contributions, for libraries it may be recognition of their financial contributions and services, for publishers it may be revenue and greater partnership with institutions, etc.
- **Assume goodwill, increase understanding, and seek win-win outcomes.** Uncertainty and confusion can lead to risk aversion, with stakeholders opting for traditional models over OA due to perceived complexities and unknowns. Remember that everything is a matter of perspective: one stakeholder's perception is unlikely to be the same as other stakeholders'. Even if a publisher (or another stakeholder) intends to make a specific change, the infrastructure may not yet be in place to enable that to happen.
- **Multi-stakeholder conversations are essential** and cannot practically be spearheaded by smaller and specialist publishers, although they are important stakeholders to include. This is a role for libraries, publishers, and subject associations together, and research funders can usefully play a convening and facilitating role. Standards bodies also have an important role to play in stimulating change throughout the supply chain to properly support OA book publishing. Without this cross-stakeholder collaboration, neither libraries nor publishers will be able to transition successfully.

Affordable and accessible to diverse researchers, research organizations, funders, and those beyond academia.

All stakeholders should:

- Align around short to medium-term support for all of the current most useful OA book publishing revenue models (i.e. BPCs, digital format freemium, print sales with online OA, and consortial models).

- Use BPCs to fund only first-copy production expenses. BPCs can provide flexibility for smaller and specialist publishers.
- Stimulate the evolution of consortial funding models to be more inclusive of smaller and specialist book publishers in transition to OA.
- Continue to evolve consortial models which enjoy the strongest cross-stakeholder support and are most promising for the medium to long term. These models need to evolve to be better integrated with library acquisition workflows and to better support smaller and specialist book publishers in transition to OA.

Funders should:

- Support the implementation of these recommendations by incorporation, where relevant, into OA mandates.

Librarians should:

- Articulate how OA books enable and support their own readers.
- Raise awareness amongst their faculty of the OA book publishing schemes the library supports financially.
- Ask consortia to support more collective funding models and to support more small and specialist book publishers to transition to OA.
- Establish a rolling fund for OA book publishing from their acquisition budget.
- Allocate funding to consortial funding models further in advance of publication so that there is a stable pot of money available for allocation to collections.
- Invest any year-end money in consortial funding models for upcoming books.
- Request from intermediaries more transparency and frequent reporting for progress on consortial funding offers.
- Use purchasing plans to prioritize print acquisition of books where the digital version is OA, particularly those published by smaller and specialized publishers in transition to OA.

Consortia such as Jisc should:

- Create procurement frameworks to help streamline the process of vetting consortial funding, digital format freemium, and print sales with online OA offers, reducing the need for assessments by individual institutions.
- Enhance their capacity to interact meaningfully with the long tail of smaller and specialist publishers.

Publishers and the supply chain should:

- Seek an OA transition, not the addition of a new revenue stream.
- Let libraries and funders know immediately if they plan to commission a book from an affiliated author.
- Provide librarians with a central place to find, browse, and fund consortial funding models.
- Align with the cOAlition S Equitable Pricing framework to foster global equity in scholarly publishing⁵.

Enabled by infrastructure that is fit for purpose and embedded in library, publisher, and supply chain partner workflows.

All stakeholders should:

⁵ <https://www.coalition-s.org/pricing-framework-to-foster-global-equity-in-scholarly-publishing/>

- Invest in infrastructure, whether commercial or community-owned, that is standards-based, interoperable, and sustainable for all stakeholders.
- Evolve the existing book supply chain to optimize for OA book publishing.
- Use key services including:
 - DOAB and OAPEN <https://www.doabooks.org/> and <https://www.oapen.org/>
 - Global Item Reports in COUNTER Release 5.1 <https://cop5.projectcounter.org/en/5.1/04-reports/04-item-reports.html> and Open Access eBook Usage (OAeBU) Data Trust pilot project <https://www.oabookusage.org>.
 - OA Switchboard, which will enable publishers to send pre-publication funding eligibility enquiry messages to research funders and institutions, who in turn can respond. It will also allow for publication notification messages to be sent by publishers to research funders and institutions. <https://www.oaswitchboard.org/oabookspilot>
 - Thoth, which supports open metadata creation and exchange and is optimized for smaller academic publishers. <https://thoth.pub/>

Transparent, leading to communication, confidence, and trust between authors, funders, libraries, and publishers.

Funders should support this by convening cross-stakeholder workshops to:

- Enable stakeholders to understand and work together to resolve inconsistencies about how book information is exchanged between publisher and intermediaries, intermediaries and intermediaries, or intermediaries and libraries in the supply chain.
- Identify ways in which a shared understanding of how many books are published each year, how many of these are academic books, and how many of these are published OA, can be established.
- Establish whether infrastructure to provide information about price and services, for example the Journal Comparison Service⁶, could usefully evolve to include OA books.
- Leverage the PALOMERA knowledge base to improve the discoverability of information about funder, institutional, and publisher policies for OA books.

And a world in which books are:

Quality-assured, so that scholars can rely on and build on the work of others. Although practices may change, the transition to OA in itself does not – and should not – compromise editorial or production standards.

All stakeholders should:

- Champion and maintain strict quality standards in OA book publishing.
- Overcome any author scepticism about the quality of OA publishing. There can be good publishers and poor publishers under any revenue model, and any problems are with the actors and not the model. Nevertheless, problems of perception are important to acknowledge and address and it is true that the lower barriers to entry for OA publishing open the door more widely for less experienced and less well-intentioned actors. Transparency of practice, adherence to editorial standards, and alignment with OASPA criteria and requirements⁷, are essential.

⁶ <https://www.coalition-s.org/journal-comparison-service/>

⁷ <https://www.oaspa.org/apply/membership-criteria/>

- Embed links to the Think. Check. Submit. checklist for books and chapters, which is a tool authors can use to assess if they are submitting their research to a trusted publisher. The checklist helps authors not only to avoid bad actors, but also to assess the most relevant publishers for their field of work. <https://thinkchecksubmit.org/books-and-chapters/>
- Consider whether DOAB has a role to play in quality assurance, as DOAJ does for journals.

Findable and usable, with researchers' work being more widely read and used, in both digital and print.

Publishers and the supply chain should:

- Invest resources in metadata creation, supply, access, and use. OA books need to be visible both in the established supply chain *and* in the OA-specific supply chain (i.e. via DOAB and OAPEN). One promising open metadata tool is Thoth, which is optimized for smaller academic publishers. <https://thoth.pub/>
- Update OA status changes, OA licences, and the unique identifiers for related authors, employers, and funders, and convey this information correctly throughout the supply chain.
- Enable librarians to have a central place to find, browse, and access OA books or packages.

Reusable under an open licence, typically a Creative Commons licence (CC licence).

Publishers and the supply chain should:

- Ensure the correct licence is available on full-text and in metadata.
- Update and surface changes made during the lifecycle of a book.

Preserved as part of our shared long-term cultural and intellectual heritage.

Publishers should:

- Ensure OA books are preserved in trusted long-term archives such as CLOCKSS and Portico.
- Add preservation location and status information to their ONIX metadata feeds.

Libraries should:

- Include digital preservation language in their contracts for book acquisition – <https://liblicense.crl.edu/resources/digital-preservation/>

Funders should:

- Incorporate requirements for long-term digital preservation into guidance, mandates, and policy requirements.

Impactful, so that academia and society progress more broadly.

Funders and Librarians should:

- Convene and exchange knowledge about what has worked in demonstrating value to finance and procurement teams.

Publishers should:

- Ensure more books designed to be adopted for faculty reading lists and that support other core library use cases are published OA.

All stakeholders should:

- Actively support the Open Access eBook Usage (OAeBU) Data Trust pilot project. <https://www.oabookusage.org>

The sum of these recommendations will help to create an OA book publishing world that is sustainable for learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist academic publishers and other stakeholders.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the following people for their thoughtful engagement with this project. They, of course, may not agree with our conclusions or recommendations, nor may their organizations. We would also like to acknowledge the many anonymous respondents to the project surveys. Thank you all!

Steering Group

- Rachel Bruce (UKRI)
- Caroline Mackay (Jisc)
- Claire Redhead (OASPA)
- James Rivington (British Academy)
- Wayne Syme (ALPSP)
- Tahia Zaidi (UKRI)

Focus Groups, Interviews, and Workshops:

- Magaly Bascones (Cengage)
- Vivian Berghahn (Berghahn Books)
- Cassie Bowman (University of the Arts)
- David Brickner (EBSCO)
- Dominic Broadhurst (University of Salford)
- Justyna Burzynska (University of the Arts)
- Yvonne Campfens (OA Switchboard)
- Stephen Carlton (University of Manchester)
- Fiona Carr (CCC)
- Tom Dark, Edinburgh University Press
- Simon Davies (Modern Humanities Research Association)
- Novin Doostdar (OneWorld Publications)
- Ixchel Faniel (OCLC)
- Noam Fass (Ex Libris, Clarivate)
- Rebecca Fisher (English Association)
- Oliver Gadsby (Gadsby Online)
- Lanette Garza (NERL)
- Rupert Gatti (Open Book Publishers)
- Rebecca Gower (Cambridge University)
- Tom Grady (Birkbeck, University of London / Copim Project)
- Neil Grindley (Jisc)
- Sean Guynes (Lever Press)
- Oliver Hamilton (Google Scholar)
- Claire Holloway (OCLC)
- Janet Joyce (Equinox Publishing Limited)
- Jane Kelly (Cambridge University)
- Paula Kennedy (University of London Press)
- Kirsi Keravuori (The Finnish Literature Society)
- Alan Kinder (Regional Studies Association)
- Dev Kumar (OA Switchboard)
- Sharla Lair (Lyrisis)
- A. Lawrence (Royal Geographical Society)
- Young Lee (Berghahn Books)
- Beth Logan (University of Sussex)
- Ruth Mallalieu (Oxford University)
- Sarah McDonald (Edinburgh University Press)
- Valerie McCutcheon (University of Glasgow)
- Lisa McLaren (SCONUL)
- Max Mosterd (Knowledge Unlatched / Wiley)
- Jim O'Donnell (Arizona State University)
- Gavin Phillips (SUPC/University of Reading)
- Ros Pyne (Bloomsbury)
- James Rice (The White Horse Press)
- Steve Sharp (Sheffield Hallam University)
- Heather Sherman (BDS)
- Laura Simonite (EMS Press)
- Elaine Sykes (University of Lancaster)
- Richard Taylor (Bath Spa University)
- Michael Thickett (Emerald Publishing)
- Alex Thomson (English Association)
- Alessandra Tosi (Open Book Publishers)
- Stephanie Veldman (DeGruyter Brill)
- S J Walker (University of Manchester)
- James Watson (Taylor & Francis)
- Abeni Wickham (SciFree)
- Tim Williams (Edward Elgar Publishing)

We are grateful to the following people for additional comments on the Vision Statement:

- James Bisset
- Ruth Harrison
- Pierre Lasou
- Holly Limbert
- Vincent Oei
- Martin Wolf

We are also grateful to Digital Science for access to Dimensions <https://www.digital-science.com/product/dimensions>.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

Members of the project team are involved in various capacities with some of the services mentioned or recommended in this report: CLOCKSS, DOAB, OAPEN, and Think. Check. Submit.

Appendix 1 – Interviews and Focus Groups

We interviewed publishers of different types, sizes, and disciplines in order to understand the opportunities and obstacles in publishing OA academic books. We aimed to gather their insights on the tools that would aid them in transitioning to OA. The feedback from these publishers was varied, presenting a wide range of perspectives and practices. As might be expected, some views gathered through interviews and surveys contradict one another, while others raise concerns that seem to have already been addressed. However, highlighting these differing perspectives and experiences is crucial for fully understanding the stakeholders' issues and developing tools to effectively address their needs.

We also facilitated focus groups with stakeholders, including small publishers with little experience of OA books, librarians, intermediaries, and metadata experts. One important theme of the library focus group was the many challenges of discovering OA books and making them available to library users. The supply chain and metadata focus groups suggested there may be ways to enhance the discovery of OA books, and these ideas are developed further in the guide.

Publisher interviews

We invited a diverse group of smaller and specialist publishers of different types, from an array of disciplines, and with different levels of experience with OA book publishing.

Those we interviewed:

- Include independent academic publishers, family-owned businesses, subject associations, university libraries, and one former independent publishing house now owned by an investment firm.
- Publish in fields such as archaeology, anthropology, business, business management, cultural history, economics, environmental studies, English literature, humanities, linguistics, religious studies, social sciences, and theology.
- Are at different stages of adopting OA publishing. Some are fully or predominantly OA, others have only published a few OA titles, and some have not yet ventured into OA publishing.
- Have different relationships with library customers, ranging from those with strong connections to those with little experience in this area.

The interviews were carried out in two stages. During the first stage, our focus was on identifying the main opportunities and challenges in transitioning to OA. In the second stage, we delved deeper into these issues and the issues that arose from our literature review, and we asked about the tools and guidance required to support their transition.

At one end of the spectrum were those publishers who fully and/or routinely publish OA books. One publisher was already fully OA. Another was almost fully OA yet ensures that there is room in their program for authors and projects that are not yet ready for full OA or for books with image catalogues that cannot be OA due to third-party rights issues. One publisher said their decision to transition to OA was to avoid risk by 'getting ahead of the curve'.

Other publishers we spoke to tend to adopt OA selectively. They carefully consider which books to publish in OA to ensure there is adequate financial support, that publishing the book OA aligns with authors and meets a need in terms of improved impact, mission alignment, and/or their sustainability goals.

At the other end of the spectrum, two publishers raised serious concerns about any transition to OA publishing. They were concerned about the impact on their relationship with authors, and the risk of turning this into a transactional relationship rather than a collaborative and scholarly endeavour. Another publisher was concerned that if an author is paying to publish there is a potential conflict with maintaining reliability and high standards in academic publishing. These publishers were also concerned by author misunderstandings about OA policies. Funding was perceived as a significant barrier, with copyright and third-party rights seen as another formidable challenge.

These varied perspectives highlight the need to address a range of needs and concerns when supporting smaller and specialized book publishers to transition to OA.

Engaging with Libraries

The relationship between academic libraries and publishers is crucial for the financial support, dissemination, and success of OA books. Insights from various publishers reveal diverse strategies and challenges here.

Communications and marketing with and to libraries are new requirements for OA book publishing, and many smaller book publishers (larger ones too) simply do not know very much about their customers. This is a marketplace with many intermediaries from whom libraries purchase collections of books due to the overwhelming volume of books and potential transactions. Publishers can struggle to promote OA (or indeed any) books to libraries due to a lack of capacity, experience, and skills. One publisher saw the opportunities for a grassroots approach, emphasizing that smaller publishers are in an excellent position to build trust and transparent communication, and to prioritize the needs of authors and research communities. They foster relationships with libraries, faculty, department editors, and contributors.

In certain important international markets, librarians who purchase a collection of books evaluate return-on-investment by determining the value of each book's sale price individually. Even though the publisher will not have charged for the OA books in the collection, the librarians consider them to have no value and so do not factor them into the return-on-investment calculations. For this reason, it can be difficult or even impossible to sell collections of books that include both OA and non-OA books. The solution is often to remove the OA books from these collections, which exacerbates problems with the visibility and use of OA books.

Platforms like JSTOR, EBSCO, and ProQuest are crucial for many of the publishers we spoke to in getting books into library supply channels and ensuring their OA books appear alongside other ebooks for researchers. However, some publishers are concerned about whether the future costs to place books on these platforms will be sustainable.

Separate infrastructure exists for OA, which is helpful and also problematic, because it is not well integrated with the established supply chain. The Open Book Collective, funded by Research England Development Fund (Research England is part of UKRI) and Arcadia, provides a centralized platform where librarians can choose to support packages of OA books that include titles from all participating publishers, or they can opt to support individual publisher programmes. This consortial funding model aims to streamline and formalize funding streams and support mechanisms, making it easier for libraries to participate. But platforms such as these are in an entirely different ecosystem from the well-established supply chain. Better integration is needed.

Revenue Models

The landscape of revenue models for OA book publishing is diverse, reflecting the varied needs and circumstances of different publishers. Although a rich mixture of revenue models is available, consortial funding models appear to both librarians and publishers to

have the most likelihood of success. These do not depend on authors having access to funds and have the potential to provide a steady and predictable revenue stream in the same way that traditional library sales have done. Most publishers preferred to adopt at least two revenue models rather than putting all their eggs in one basket. The key driver for this was a real concern about sustainability.

Most of the publishers we interviewed use a mix of revenue models, including:

Book Processing Charges (BPCs): This revenue model is not favoured by funders or librarians due to concerns about equity in access to publishing services. Some of the publishers who participated in our focus group also shared these concerns. However, BPCs are widely deployed. Many publishers charge them for authors who have funding. The challenges are greater when academic book authors lack the funds to cover publication fees.

Chapter Processing Charges (CPCs): Edited books are important in some disciplines, for example in the social sciences. Many publishers offer CPCs for authors who have funding and wish to comply with OA policies. Several publishers reported reducing the cost of a book to reflect the number of OA chapters; others said that no price adjustment is made in this respect.

Consortial Funding Models: These initiatives can be beneficial for smaller publishers seeking to scale up or transition. By centralizing the management of library memberships and other support mechanisms, publishers can focus more on their core activities –publishing high-quality academic content. Collaborating with intermediaries that specialize in this space can provide access to libraries and their purchasing power, thereby expanding the number and reach of OA books. These approaches can help smaller publishers to raise funds for OA publishing and increase the discovery and visibility of the resulting books. However, publishers are uncertain about how sustainable these models will be in the long-term. Several publishers who had explored consortial funding models concluded that the revenue share through these schemes was not sufficient to cover their costs.

Institutional and grant funding for diamond publishing: This revenue model supports publishing programmes or book series that are in line with the funder's mission. The publishers we spoke to who deploy this model appreciate the support they receive. However, they rarely rely on it exclusively. Many employ other revenue models as well to avoid over-relying on any single funder. This is because grant funding is not always secure in the long term and cannot be assumed to be guaranteed. There are also administrative challenges in keeping track of different funding durations (e.g. one-year vs. three-year pledges).

Library Memberships: An increasing number of publishers have launched membership programmes to provide an additional revenue stream. The aim is for the publisher to spread the costs of producing OA books across many supporting institutions. One full OA publisher we spoke to reported that their library membership is a key component of their business and contributes over a third of their total income. However, running such a scheme can be a resource-intensive challenge for small publishers, and increasingly they prefer to share this task, for example through The Open Book Collective.

Print sales remain a valuable revenue stream for some OA books. One publisher noted that when the OA web publishing movement began, there was an assumption that increased visibility would boost print sales, creating a win-win situation. However, the reality has proven more complex. When print sales were discussed in the context of OA books, publishers were unable to identify if an increase or decrease in usual sales was the impact of the OA model, or other factors, such as the popularity of a given title, or a general decline in print sales. One publisher told us that they only make paperback

copies available of OA books to ensure that the print is affordable for library customers. Publishers may also adopt different pricing approaches for print in the presence of OA (e.g. lower paperback prices for print to encourage sales despite online OA, or higher hardback prices in order to capture revenue from libraries despite online OA.)

Authors

Publishers reported that many authors do not fully understand OA publishing terms and concepts, leading to confusion and challenges with policy compliance. Publishers create educational toolkits covering the basics of OA publishing and provide clear guidance on what authors need to discuss with OA teams at their institutions. This means that authors are bombarded with conflicting information and terms, which adds to the cacophony.

Publishers reported that key concerns from authors revolve around quality, prestige, licensing options, and copyright issues. Some of these issues concern digital publication, rather than OA specifically, with a feeling that this led to less rigorous production standards. In some disciplines the printed copy is valued particularly highly – one author said, for example, 'It's disappointing when they receive a book that has come off a printer instead of a high-quality hardback.' Publishers were also worried about a reduction in quality, especially where the BPC model is used, resulting in a more transactional rather than creative collaboration between publisher and author. Another publisher expressed the concern that the BPC model could lead to a decrease in quality because publishers might prioritize quantity in order to make money through OA. One publisher said that authors have raised concerns that OA is 'vanity publishing' and a way for universities to take ownership of their IP.

That said, all the publishers we spoke to emphasized that their own OA books go through the same rigorous peer review processes as their own publications, to ensure high quality. They are committed to maintaining their reputation and serving our authors. Another said that ongoing conversations with authors who may initially resist OA publishing can help address concerns and demonstrate the benefits through sample reports showing readership, scope, and reach.

Copyright and Licensing

By offering various licensing options, one publisher aims to give authors the flexibility to choose how their works are used and shared. This is especially important as some authors are concerned about potential misuse or misattribution of their work under Creative Commons licences⁸. Clear communication about the implications and protections provided by these licences can help alleviate these concerns.

Some publishers are concerned about institutional retention of intellectual property rights, seeing this as an unnecessary complication. Another reported that authors often face challenges when caught between institutional policies regarding OA publishing, with the publisher needing to engage with their institution to understand the specific issues at hand and provide tailored support to authors navigating these policies.

Publishers expressed concern that Green OA policies can conflict with their plans by reducing the effective sales period for a book and therefore have the potential to undermine the sustainability of existing revenue models. Publishers would prefer to collaborate with libraries to make final publications OA through the Gold route. Some reported recent examples of receiving rather aggressive letters from librarians regarding rights retention when there is not a funder requirement for a book to be published OA, and perceived that this was intended to drive down costs rather than to facilitate OA.

⁸ <https://creativecommons.org/>

Metadata and the Supply Chain

Some publishers are aware of the importance of good metadata to ensure their books are discoverable, but struggle to identify and overcome challenges. One reason for this is that, throughout our research, we consistently heard three different use cases being conflated: discovery of books by libraries who can provide funding to make them OA, discovery of OA books by readers, and discovery of OA books by those tracking compliance with OA mandates.

Ensuring transparency is a challenge. Publishers who supply OA information in their book metadata cannot see how that metadata flows through the supply chain and appears in library-facing services and systems. This is a source of frustration for OA book publishers of all sizes because they are unsure if their metadata has been correctly picked up and they are unable to identify and correct problems. Some of the publishers we spoke to over-rely on libraries to visit their websites to discover what OA (and indeed other) books are on offer. However, librarians cannot systematically browse publisher websites for OA books. Occasional visits to individual publishers' websites occur only for specific books requested by faculty.

Ebook aggregators are integral to the book supply chain, and in ensuring that OA books are discoverable. Libraries depend on these vendors to provide records and curated collections to avoid dealing with books at a title level. Vendors like GOBI Library Solutions and Ebook Central are used but have limitations. Librarians have a sense that aggregators do not care about OA books, because they cannot find information about OA availability. However, the situation is more complex. While some publishers share OA information in the metadata with aggregators, others do not. One aggregator informed us that they are working on creating metadata that indicates the OA status of a book. They are doing this in response to demands from library customers. This work is time-consuming because they need to verify if a book is OA by locating the licence through CrossRef. Also, not all aggregators treat publishers in the same way. For example, some give publishers royalties for both their OA books and their non-OA books, and others do not, so publishers are not equally incentivized to push a book through all channels.

ONIX is the lifeblood of the book supply chain. Many publishers do not fully understand the ONIX metadata standard and smaller publishers are least likely to have in-house metadata experts to rely upon. This results in many mistakes, for example placing information about a book's OA status in a free text field rather than the specific ONIX field created for this purpose. And different versions of the ONIX standard are in use in different parts of the supply chain.

Organizations such as BDS and OCLC and many aggregators play helpful roles. They ingest ONIX from publishers, normalize data, and provide subscribing libraries with MARC records. Unfortunately, these organizations are not set up to work with small book publishers. DOAB and OAPEN play an important role in helping smaller publishers ensure that their books are discoverable. Both produce open MARC records and KBART files.

Publishers of book collections often provide KBART files. Only if every book in the collection is OA would the creators of MARC records classify this as an OA collection. If there are some paywalled titles and some OA titles in a collection, the KBART records wouldn't convey this.

Open Book Futures and COPIM support Thoth, which enables OA publishers to generate metadata records including ONIX, MARC, and KBART. Further integration of Thoth in the supply chain would be beneficial. It is early days for this initiative and greater visibility and marketing could help it scale up.

Publishers of hybrid books, where only some chapters are OA, provide book level rather than chapter level metadata, especially for curated edited volumes in the humanities and social sciences (HSS), to ensure the full title is discoverable. Chapter level metadata would facilitate discovery, but can be an expensive and difficult lift for even very large publishers.

Publishers that retrospectively convert books to OA report that updating the metadata is a laborious, manual process. Despite their efforts, the revised metadata is often not pushed through the supply chain by intermediaries. Ebook aggregators and the organizations that create MARC records reported that they do not receive updated metadata about books that have flipped from non-OA to OA. So, once these books are in the supply chain, it is impossible for libraries to discover correct information about their status.

There is no standard vocabulary for book revenue models that is shared throughout the supply chain. This adds to the confusion and messiness.

Tools that would help publishers transition to OA
Publishers have diverse needs when transitioning to OA, but the following requests emerged repeatedly during our research:

Balancing Traditional and OA Publishing: Publishers face the challenge of managing traditional print backlists while developing OA books. Limited capacity and funding require careful prioritization to balance these activities. They find it difficult to prioritize and would like a practical playbook or a ten-point checklist to help them prioritize tasks and choose the right platforms and providers.

OA revenue models: A simple reference guide to the revenue models for OA books, as there are many publications and researching these is time-consuming.

Challenges in Metadata and Supply Chain: The publishers we spoke to are not metadata experts and do not understand where the issues are. However, they are open to receiving guidance and a detailed introduction on how to enhance their metadata creation and ensure smooth transition through the supply chain.

Selection Guide: Different providers offer varied services, including metadata, distribution tools, pricing structures, and regional visibility. Publishers need a guide to help them assess their needs and choose the most suitable providers.

Educational toolkits for authors: This toolkit should provide comprehensive information, covering policies, distribution chains, and data accessibility to help authors understand OA publishing policies, distribution chains, copyright and the implications of different funding models.

Advice in addressing Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) Issues: Publishers would appreciate clear guidelines on improving economic equity (e.g. the cOAlition S Equitable Pricing Framework).

Advice on library engagement and marketing: Independent small publishers have little experience in communicating directly to libraries because the sale of print and ebooks to libraries has been through intermediaries.

Usage data: Publishers want to share usage data with supporting libraries and authors. Authors are increasingly interested in accessing usage data for their books, particularly if they have contributed to BPCs. Providing authors with visually compelling usage data statements, similar to royalty statements, can enhance transparency and accountability in the OA publishing process. However, publishers report challenges in representing the

data in a non-confusing way due to varying data collection methods and the fact that their books may be on multiple platforms.

Librarian interviews

Librarians told us that a transition to OA can offer significant benefits for both publishers and libraries, and there is substantial interest and support from libraries for this shift. However, libraries face complexities and challenges when supporting OA books or making them discoverable to their users, supporting OA infrastructure, and supporting OA membership and collaborative schemes.

A key issue for libraries is the relevance of the content. There is a perception that the selection of titles for OA schemes is often driven by revenue protection rather than a genuine commitment to OA. Librarians reported that publishers often describe their models as innovative and exciting, but they typically involve purchasing collections that might become OA eventually, with no clear revenue or other targets disclosed for this threshold to be reached. Much of the content in OA packages offered by consortial funding models is seen as peripheral. Libraries align their selection of books with the support of teaching and learning and open research. Many publishers align their OA book provision with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which some librarians interpret as a supplier-led approach. Instead libraries want to provide OA to books on reading lists and acquire content aligned with their broader strategies (e.g. supporting Open Educational Resources). Librarians advise publishers that faculty reading lists are a key place where OA books need to appear if they are going to be used.

Librarians want greater clarity on the value of OA offers and would welcome advice about how to demonstrate this value to finance and procurement teams. They can face challenges from finance departments that require confirmation of received goods, a challenge because librarians contribute to OA schemes without being entirely certain of the specific titles that will become available. Librarians in the UK suggested a Jisc purchasing framework could help streamline the process, reducing the need for individual assessments of book publishers and their policies each time.

Librarians explained that BPCs can present challenges within institutions within institutions, as procurement and finance teams increasingly scrutinize expenditure related to OA, particularly when UKRI funds are involved. The allocation of these funds requires careful documentation and thorough assessment to ensure compliance with policy guidelines. Librarians suggested that a Jisc framework could help streamline this process and enhance efficiency.

Some publishers receive requests from contributors to an edited collection asking about the possibility of their chapter being made OA for a Chapter Processing Charge (CPC). However, librarians are not keen on hybrid books where some chapters are OA and others are not. Incorporating an OA chapter, and not the other paywalled chapters, in their catalogues was potentially confusing to users, and caused users to seek out the rest of the book which the library may not have purchased.

Librarians told us they generally prefer ebooks to print due to ease of access and convenience, but print versions are still purchased when necessary. Paperbacks are favoured over hardbacks due to budget constraints. Librarians were clear that having an OA book would not always discourage libraries from buying print copies. Students often prefer printed books for their courses, which drives the decision to buy print versions. Print versions are also purchased to address specific accessibility needs for readers, ensuring all students and researchers have access to the required materials. There is increasing concern about the use of plastic and packaging materials for print resources.

Libraries are considering these factors in their purchasing decisions, with a preference for more sustainable options.

Librarians prefer to discover the availability of OA books through their library discovery services such as Alma. This enables them to switch on OA collections and books, making them discoverable by users. However, switching on all OA collections in library management systems can result in duplication in library catalogues. Currently, they discover the availability of OA books in an ad-hoc way – for example, through emails from publishers announcing new lists of OA books. Faculty librarians sometimes stumble across OA books or discover them through specific requests from academics. The process of discovering and integrating OA books in library systems is labour-intensive and messy.

Focus Groups

Focus Group 1 – 22 April 2024 Summary

Key discussion points:

1. **Diamond Publishing Model:** While desirable because it allows authors to publish without paying, participants noted its limitations, particularly the difficulty in scaling.
2. **Book Processing Charges (BPCs):** Participants noted a lack of funding for BPCs and were hesitant to pursue this route, viewing it as inequitable, especially since many of their authors lack funding.
3. **Pace of Change:** The rapid pace of change was a concern, with institutional mandates and rights retention policies creating challenges. One participant mentioned that authors, unfamiliar or uncomfortable with OA, are being pushed to publish with zero-embargo Green OA. They emphasized the need for more time to develop sustainable models. Another participant felt that Green OA policies were undermining their efforts and preferred collaborating with libraries to make the version of record open.
4. **Funding Challenges for Small Institutes:** A participant from a small institute that publishes only a few books annually highlighted significant funding constraints. They rely on inconsistent BA funding and donations. Retired academics at the institute, who often write these books, are marginalized as they cannot access typical funding opportunities. Authors from outside the UK face different mandates and funding streams, further complicating efforts. Despite supporting OA in principle, financial limitations are a significant barrier.
5. **Copyright and Third-Party Rights:** Another participant expressed frustration with developing an OA policy in the architecture field, where copyright and third-party rights are complex. Rights holders are accustomed to specific licensing terms (e.g. English language only, 100-copy print run) and are reluctant to relinquish control, deterring attempts to pursue OA.

Library Market Importance and Sales Channels:

- **Library Sales:** Participants acknowledged the importance of the academic library market for both print and electronic sales. One participant is experimenting with low-cost trade editions via Amazon for their OA books, noting that OA editions might unlock new revenue channels, though the marketing is still in its early stages. Retrospective conversion to OA was noted as challenging, particularly when libraries have already purchased titles.
- **Ebook Revenue:** Another participant stated that the majority of their ebook revenue comes from libraries, with additional sales through their website and EBSCO, which flags OA books.

- Open Book Collective: One participant explored the Open Book Collective but found the financial return insufficient to cover costs. They expressed scepticism about library budgets truly shifting to fund OA, seeing current efforts as temporary rather than a long-term commitment to sustainable OA book publishing.
- Knowledge Unlatched: Another participant mentioned using Knowledge Unlatched for backlist or out-of-print books. While it was effective for publicity and raising awareness, the financial returns were limited.

Priority Areas for Transition and Discoverability:

Participants identified tools and guidance that could aid in the transition to OA, with library engagement and marketing emerging as top priorities.

Focus Group 2 – Libraries, 9th May 2024 Summary

Key discussion points:

1. Financial Support for OA Books:
 - Libraries have varying experiences with funding OA books. Some only invest leftover budget at year-end, while others have prioritized OA but haven't fully implemented this yet. Libraries are developing policies for membership schemes, with some integrating OA support into broader strategies.
 - Concerns were raised about the suitability of some schemes due to high costs or irrelevant content. There was criticism of publishers focusing on revenue rather than core OA titles.
2. Procurement Challenges:
 - Issues with procurement and finance teams were highlighted, especially regarding schemes like Knowledge Unlatched (KU) where it's unclear how many books will be available. Libraries face pushback when using UKRI funds for BPCs, requiring careful accounting.
 - Procurement departments dislike APCs and BPCs being paid via credit cards, creating ongoing friction. A unified approach, such as a Jisc framework, was suggested to ease these challenges.
3. Discovery of OA Books:
 - Discovering OA books is challenging; librarians often rely on publisher emails or stumble upon titles. While some libraries use Alma's discovery tools, there is a need for better integration of OA books into mainstream library collections.
 - OA books are often siloed within libraries, with subject librarians sometimes unaware of OA schemes. Training sessions are planned to improve this integration.
4. Direct Acquisition from Publishers:
 - Librarians occasionally visit publisher websites for specific OA titles but lack the capacity to browse systematically. They prefer getting metadata from library vendors, as managing OA books is currently labor-intensive.
5. Print vs. Digital Purchasing:
 - OA availability doesn't deter libraries from purchasing print copies, especially if titles are on reading lists or needed for accessibility. Post-COVID, print purchases have declined, with financial conditions favoring paperbacks.
 - Environmental concerns, such as the use of plastic in packaging, are influencing decisions between hardback and paperback.
6. Metadata and Discovery:

- Librarians emphasized the importance of accurate ONIX metadata for ease of discovery. They advised publishers to prioritize good metadata, get books on reading lists, and understand library purchasing behaviors.
7. Transition to OA:
- Librarians urged publishers, especially smaller ones, to be bold and innovative in transitioning to OA, rather than mimicking large publishers. Collaboration with libraries on new models is encouraged.
 - Publishers should avoid conflating open access with digital issues and focus on being easy to work with, aligning with libraries' administrative workflows.
8. Chapterized OA Books:
- These were criticized for adding confusion, as current library systems struggle to manage content at the chapter level.

Advice to Publishers:

- Be forward-looking and bold in developing OA models.
- Prioritize metadata and discoverability.
- Engage with faculty librarians to ensure books appear on reading lists.
- Be mindful of libraries' workflows and procurement challenges.
- Collaborate with libraries, particularly on non-BPC models, and support bibliodiversity.

Focus Groups 3 and 4 – Supply Chain Experts, 14 and 17 June 2024 Summary

Key discussion points:

Metadata Consistency and Challenges: The quality and consistency of metadata records vary widely, with no significant difference between OA and non-OA books. Metadata is often not resupplied to libraries when the OA status of books changes. For OA collections, if even one book isn't OA, the collection might not be classified as OA in KBART files.

Chapter-Level Metadata: Publishers currently do not provide good chapter-level metadata, hindering the ability to communicate the OA status at the chapter level. Refreshing metadata for flipped chapters should be done using BITS.

ONIX Metadata Issues:

1. ONIX metadata feeds often lack standardization, especially for OA. While ONIX contains detailed information (e.g. book weight), much of it is irrelevant to libraries. Moreover, ONIX feeds are minimal and inconsistent, especially from small publishers.
 - Some OA metadata gets lost in the supply chain, with platforms like Amazon not accepting OA-specific fields. This forces publishers to mislabel OA books as zero-priced instead of properly structuring their ONIX feeds.
2. Support for Small Publishers:
 - Small publishers struggle with the burden of sending ONIX feeds to multiple platforms, each with different requirements. DOAB and OAPEN play critical roles in supporting these smaller publishers, helping to manage relationships and streamline metadata dissemination.
 - There is no standard vocabulary for revenue models of OA books, which complicates metadata communication further.
3. Revenue Models and Incentives:

- Some publishers receive royalties for OA books from aggregators, which might reduce their incentive to distribute metadata through multiple channels. DOAB's efforts to assess the quality of OA books are valuable in addressing concerns about the potential rise in poor-quality publications.
4. Quality of Metadata Records:
 - The quality of metadata records varies, and ensuring 'fitness for purpose' is becoming more crucial. NISO provides guidelines on communicating about OA, which could help standardize metadata quality across the board.
 5. Need for Better Communication:
 - There is a need for improved visibility and understanding between libraries and publishers regarding each other's metadata processes. Sharing examples and conducting further research, like OCLC's ongoing efforts, could foster better dialogue and cooperation.
 6. Metadata Consistency and Challenges:
 - The quality and consistency of metadata records vary widely, with no significant difference between OA and non-OA books.
 - Metadata is often not resupplied to libraries when the OA status of books changes. For OA collections, if even one book isn't OA, the collection might not be classified as OA in KBART files.
 7. Chapter-Level Metadata:
 - Publishers currently do not provide good chapter-level metadata, hindering the ability to communicate the OA status at the chapter level. Refreshing metadata for flipped chapters should be done using BITS.
 8. Conclusion: The discussion highlighted the complexities and inconsistencies in OA metadata management, particularly for small publishers. Participants emphasized the need for better standardization, clearer communication, and stronger support mechanisms to optimize the supply chain for OA books.

Appendix 2 – Publisher survey results

Demographics and publishing output

There were 42 respondents to the Publisher survey. Of these, 8 were learned societies, 14 were university presses, 14 were independent publishers, and 5 were library publishers. One respondent was excluded from the analysis as they did not publish books. 34 of the publishers self-published, while 4 worked with a commercial publisher and a further 3 did both, depending on the particular project.

35 publishers produced monographs, and 33 published edited books. 19 published conference proceedings, and 18 textbooks (Figure 8). Other types of books (all in addition to one or more of the above) included toolkits, course packs, theses, scholarly editions, scholarly illustrated catalogues, commentaries, and titles for professionals, with only one or two mentioning each of these categories.

Figure 8 Types of book published

The subject areas covered are shown in Figure 9. 17 respondents published broadly across STM and HSS. A further 6 published exclusively in STM, and 19 published exclusively in the arts, social sciences and humanities.

Figure 9 Subject areas covered by publishers

There was a wide range in the number of titles (OA or non-OA) published per year, with 11 publishing 5 or fewer, 5 publishing 5-10, 13 producing 15-100, and a few larger ones

publishing 110, 200, 400, 600, or 1200 titles p.a. 15 publishers were fully OA, and 4 predominantly OA, with the remainder reporting an OA output of 33% or less of total book production.

The proportions of UK authors reported were similarly varied, with 16 reporting up to 10%, 10 reporting 20-70%, and 6 with 75-100%. The remainder weren't sure, perhaps indicating that their use of PIDs could usefully be developed.

18 respondents answered a question about what proportion of their non-OA ebook sales were made to libraries or other markets. For the majority (11), this made up 50-100% of sales. Sales to individual researchers averaged about 10%, while for another 4 sales to practitioners were significant but not huge (5-15%). One publisher sold 80% of ebooks to consumers, and another 30%, but the numbers for the others were low. Sales through channels such as Amazon are hard to analyse, as very little customer data is returned to publishers. Two publishers sold all their ebooks through such channels, with another 6 making a significant proportion of sales this way (15-50%).

37 respondents (88%) had published one or more OA titles, while 5 (12%) had yet to do so. We asked when they had published their first OA title, and again there was a wide range (even excluding the publisher who gave the rather unlikely response of 1980): answers were distributed fairly evenly from 2008 through to 2024, with just one uptick (6 publishers) in 2018.

Drivers

We asked about the drivers for publishing OA books (Figure 10). The reasons given under 'Other', besides reducing costs for textbooks for students, all fell broadly within the 'Fit with our mission' category.

Figure 10 Drivers for OA book publishing

Revenue models

We asked which revenue models were used by publishers, grouping the models as earned revenue, embedded institutional support, third-party subsidies, and consortial models.

The two most common models adopted across any of these categories were hybrid (print), where the digital version is available OA with a print version for sale (17 publishers), and BPCs (15 publishers). In the earned income category, cross-subsidy models (9) and fundraising for donations and grants (6) also featured (Figure 11). Fixed-time embargoes were used by a few (4), and two publishers used conditional embargoes (i.e. making titles OA when certain targets were hit). No publishers had found a way to fund OA titles with advertising.

Ten libraries were involved with library-based publishing, and a further 5 institutions provided subsidy funding for a university press. 4 university presses, 2 library-based presses and 2 independent publishers reported receiving third-party subsidies.

Among the consortial models (Figure 12), the most used was library crowdfunding, whereby an intermediating platform connects many purchasers with the option to unlock a title. This was used by 9 publishers.

10 publishers responded to a question about other models in use, but on examination 9 of these responses were clarifications of earlier answers or very slight variations on the options already considered (this highlights the lack of standard terminology in the field). The exception was one publisher who reported that their books were also included in Transformative Read and Publish Agreements.

It was evident that publishers were willing to, and perhaps also needed to, experiment with more than one approach. Only 7 of the 31 respondents in this section used a single revenue model, while 11 had tried two or three different approaches and a further 11 used four or more (one publisher had tried 13 different models).

Figure 11 Earned revenue models

Figure 12 Consortial models

When asked about challenges with their revenue models, 7 publishers (using a variety of models) commented that they didn't provide enough income:

'Institutional library funding does not provide enough to cover professional publishing services like developmental editing, copyediting, and layout.'

Annual funding presented a further problem:

'Institutional support is negotiated every year – difficult to make future plans as a result.'

The admin required was also an issue:

'The subscribe-to-open (backlist) model requires a lot of internal resource to coordinate; many libraries are still unfamiliar with it and it takes time to explain.'

Some models required collaboration:

'Library subscriptions, which we mostly rely on, are difficult to obtain on your own. Collaborating with other OA publishers, as we have done through the Open Book Collective, is essential.'

Three publishers noted some of the issues with BPCs:

'BPCs are still the most common model, but we're keenly aware that this route is generally only available to researchers at rich institutions, or the relatively rare AHSS researchers with grant funding, and so increases inequities in scholarly comms.'

Another publisher commented on the problem with reliance on print income:

'We have largely discontinued the 'Hybrid (print)' model as the ongoing decline in print sales/shift to digital means it is no longer sustainable.'

Some models required considerable input from authors:

'Our model requires significant investment of time from authors that is not compensated, so they must be extremely committed to the project to see it through to completion.'

And that commitment was often lacking:

'Authors are somehow sold-in to copyright-based "mainstream" models, and it can sometimes be tough to convince them that OA is actually in their interest. Sometimes difficult to convince authors about the need to adopt a certain line (e.g. crowdfunding, using CC licences, reprinting a book in time to meet the demand, etc.)'

For those publishers that used BPCs, we asked how they were structured. There were several different approaches:

- Four publishers used flat fees, in some cases tiered according to length.
- Three publishers used page rates.
- Four publishers had no specific set rates, and tailored the charges to each specific book.
- One publisher used a formula based on direct publishing costs plus a small amount for staff costs.
- Finally, one publisher had no rates at all, but simply asked authors to contribute whatever funds they could access from their institutions.

We asked whether publishers who have not yet explored any consortial funding models would be interested in learning more about them. 12 publishers indicated that they would, including 2 who had already engaged with a couple of such models but would like to learn more.

Publishing and selling OA books

We asked whether publishers had found it necessary to make changes to their workflow systems. 6 said that they had not (a couple noted that they had been OA from the start, so their workflows had been designed accordingly). 12 publishers had needed to make changes of some sort:

'OA affects almost every stage of the publication process – our bibliographic system, XML production, ebook platform, metadata feeds, distribution, invoicing etc.'

'If we involve volunteer editors, it helps. This necessitates an insertion of new persons/technologies/formats into some parts of the process.'

'We are having to introduce additional steps to make books also available through JSTOR.'

'We work on OMP for open access books, to cut costs on typesetting.'

We asked how publishers made their books discoverable by libraries. Unsurprisingly, almost all (26/29) had the books on their own websites. A little worryingly, 3 of these did not place them anywhere else. Over half also used platforms such as Knowledge Unlatched, JSTOR, MUSE, OAPEN, etc., and 8 used aggregators such as EBSCO or ProQuest. Other methods mentioned included:

- Commercial platforms ('Our commercial partner makes the content available through their online platform of our content, for a fee.')
- A discipline-specific aggregator
- Jisc Library Hub Discover
- National library databases

- Social media

The principal issues arising in making books discoverable by libraries were problems with metadata, and the resources required:

'It's been a huge amount of work to incorporate OA fields into our metadata and set up automated distribution. The supply chain is complex and the systems we use are not well adapted to OA. It's a work in progress.'

Usage data

Usage data was agreed to be essential: no publisher thought it wasn't important, and only two said it was merely 'nice to have'. The large majority (23/28) felt it was important for their own purposes, and a similarly high proportion (20/28) needed it for their authors. Only a third, however, indicated that they needed the data to report to library customers. A couple of publishers noted that funders also ask for usage data.

Despite its importance, the consensus was that getting useful data was difficult:

'It is extraordinarily time-consuming and labour-intensive, to move from one platform to the next. Not to mention the apples-and-oranges problem of different data (downloads vs. page reads, e.g.).'

Budgetary issues were an issue:

'We are interested in the new Books Analytic Dashboard but currently its costs are too high for us to afford.'

A couple of publishers working with commercial partners commented that their partners were not very helpful about passing on the data they received.

Retrospective conversion

14 publishers reported that they had converted titles retrospectively. In a couple of cases these were decades-old titles that were out of print, or already in the public domain. One publisher had made some titles OA as a response to Covid, and one had converted a book on climate change. The key factors involved were identified as funding and author willingness.

Some publishers don't seem to have had any problems with the process, but this may simply mean that they didn't encounter *additional* problems. Another publisher told us:

'In all honesty we have problems with metadata creation and distribution for immediate OA titles, so this is to an extent an extension of that problem. But it is particularly challenging to get third parties to update their records when titles flip.'

Hybrid titles

Only one of 20 respondents had published any hybrid titles. Most of that publisher's titles were hybrid, with individual chapters being covered by BPCs or Transformative Read & Publish agreements:

'Our books contribute to an overall package at the chapter level rather than being individual ebooks... our package is transparently adjusted to account for OA.'

Publishers not currently publishing OA

Only a few of our respondents had not yet published any OA titles, so only very limited conclusions could be drawn from this part of the survey. A couple of these publishers planned to publish OA in future, agreeing that it would align well with their mission and allow them to serve their authors better. One saw the main risks as financial and ideological (e.g. a mismatch with views on OA in their field), while the other was more concerned about the practicalities.

One of the publishers with no plans for OA appeared to conflate this with the BPC revenue model and commented:

'Our book series is published as a member benefit. Appetite for OA for our books from authors is currently very low – therefore making our book series OA would not be financially viable.'

Outcomes and challenges

Increased usage, author satisfaction, and increased reader engagement were held to be the most important indicators of success for an OA programme (Figure 13). Increased citations were felt to be a useful metric by just over half the respondents. Strengthening the list and financial return were each important outcomes for about a third of publishers.

Figure 13 Indicators of success

Also mentioned were:

- Funder satisfaction.
- Extending global reach.
- Reaching new audiences outside academia.
- Meeting strategic objectives to support ECRs.

The effect of OA on print sales varied from publisher to publisher. 7 reported reduced print sales, with the size of the drop varying from 15-20% to 40-50%. A further 4 publishers felt it had little or no effect. Just one reported that their print sales had been positively affected.

In terms of the problems encountered in OA publishing, the most common response (8/22) was the challenge of securing sufficient funding. Getting reader engagement and overcoming both institutional and author prejudice were also mentioned. Metadata and the problems of adapting workflows both came up again, and one respondent mentioned the challenge of creating an OA culture at a publisher which had not had to deal with OA previously. Several publishers commented on what they would do differently if starting now:

- Adopt an open source platform under their own control.
- Get an approved five-year strategy and buy-in from the University at the outset.
- Establish in-house IT/technical support.
- Pursue additional outlets from the beginning, to raise discoverability.

The following resources would have been found helpful:

- Details of funders and mandates.
- Robust guidance on best practice for developing OA contracts.
- Better metadata creation and distribution practices.
- Better usage collection and normalization.
- Review/comparison of publishing software and hosted services available.
- A toolkit on marketing.

Finally, one publisher commented:

'The idea of publishing on a possibly cheaper platform seems financially attractive, but the secure functionality, branding etc you get from going through a commercial partner is difficult to ignore.'

Appendix 3 – Library survey results

Demographics

There were 185 respondents to the library survey. Of these, 174 were libraries, 5 were consortia, 4 were research organizations, one was a professional library association, and one was an independent retired librarian.

The bulk of the responses came from the UK (78 responses, 42%) and the USA (41, 22%) from the USA. Smaller numbers were received from Australia (15), Canada (11), Germany (7) and the Netherlands (4), with a further 19 from various European countries, 7 from Central and South America, 4 from African countries, and 3 from elsewhere.

The majority (63%) were from organizations involved in both research and teaching. A further 16% focussed mainly on research, and 17% on teaching.

Supporting OA

We asked respondents to describe their approach to OA academic books. 70% agreed with the statement 'We want to improve our collection, and add OA books to our collection so we can acquire more titles at minimal cost.' There was high overlap with the 66% who agreed 'We want to support the OA book environment by supporting infrastructure initiatives such as OAPEN.' 29% fund OA book publishing for authors at their institutions (i.e. 71% do not). 15% also fund OA book publishing for authors outside their institutions, and 15% are OA book publishers themselves.

The open comments showed a range of attitudes, from a couple of institutions with strategic frameworks in place for OA support, through to one respondent who commented:

'Our stance on OA book publishing is more nuanced and agnostic ... We're not at all opposed to OA book publishing, but providing direct support for it is not a strategic priority and we are very much in a "wait and see" mode at this point.'

Regarding acquisitions, one library noted:

'Price is not usually a limiting factor, since books usually represent one-time purchases and are not usually very expensive.'

70 libraries listed the initiatives or memberships they currently participate in to support OA academic books. A total of 59 different initiatives were listed, which indicates the wide range of options available for libraries to assess and the potential demand on resources in making those assessments. The most commonly mentioned are listed in Table 4. There was considerable variation in the number of initiatives supported: many libraries reported supporting about half a dozen initiatives, but the numbers ranged from 1 to 25. Note that support might not be through paid membership or similar financial contributions but through participation and engagement. Note also that as some initiatives have multiple publishers participating, and some publishers take part in multiple initiatives, there may be some element of overlap. For example, White Horse Press participates in Open Book Collective, but also accepts direct funding for OA books. The answers were in the form of free form text. Although the survey emphasized that the focus was on books, some respondents clearly conflated this with journals – for example, 10 noted support for Open Library of Humanities, which publishes only journals.

OA initiative	No. supporters among respondents
Knowledge Unlatched*	33
Open Book Collective	31
Latin American Monographs Project (LARRP)	25
MIT Press Direct to Open	23
New Voices Awards Scheme 2021-24 (One Off Payment)	23
Open Book Futures Project	18
Open Book Publishers	18
Open Education Network	18
DOAB	17
HathiTrust	17
Central European University Press Opening the Future	15
OAPEN	15
CAUL OER initiative	14
CLACSO	14
White Horse Press	14
JSTOR Path to Open	13
University of Michigan Press: Fund to Mission	13
SCOAP3 Books	12
Bloomsbury Open Collections	11
Punctum Books	11
Open Library of Humanities	10
Open Press Tilburg University	10

Table 4 Most commonly used OA support mechanisms

*A further 4 respondents mentioned having previously supported Knowledge Unlatched.

We asked 'Which OA models work best for your library, and why?' The most popular models were diamond (14 respondents, none of whom however indicated who should fund this) and consortial funding agreements along the lines of Subscribe to Open (14 respondents). Such models need to be transparent:

'The largest concern we have is about transparency. Certain programs are not transparent about how many institutional supporters they require, when that threshold is met, and what they do with additional pledging funds.'

Models which gave access to paywalled backlist as part of the deal were preferred by five respondents, in part because it allows the library to demonstrate a direct benefit of the funding:

'Libraries support for the principle of OA by funding OA initiatives without any direct or immediate contractual benefit is something that libraries aspire to, but is not currently a good model in terms of demonstrating value for the institution.'

'Clear benefit to our institution is unfortunately becoming essential.'

There was limited support for BPCs (4 respondents), but more (9) singled these out as undesirable. There was muted support for a few other models, but five libraries (and probably others who left the question unanswered) did not feel that any of the current models worked particularly well.

In terms of making OA titles available, one librarian commented:

'We are limited in time, money and by systems, so really we can only use OA from publishers/aggregators who can host the books on easily usable and accessible platforms which interact with our discovery system and provide MARC records.'

There was little consensus as to which models might work on a larger scale. Some librarians (13) thought that the best option would be S2O [Subscribe to Open] or other collaborative models, and some (7) favoured diamond models, while again some respondents took the opportunity to speak actively against BPCs. The need to provide a concrete benefit was emphasized:

'Models most likely to work at scale are those that provide a direct and demonstrable benefit to the institutions that underwrite them. Universities need not only to do things that they can say make the world a better place generally, but also to accomplish their institutional goals – and this creates a tension when it comes to allocating limited resources.'

Problems encountered

We asked what issue (if any) respondents had found with the existing models. A number of points came up, most of them multiple times:

- Affordability was a prime concern.
- Resources: the time needed to vet models and process payments.
- Long organizational workflows.
- For institutional authors, selection for OA publication can't be assured when it is dependent on selection by a panel, on meeting the criteria of a specific collection, or on sufficient funds being raised to unlock titles at some point post-publication. A lack of guaranteed benefits for authors and readers makes demonstration of ROI problematic for institutions.
- Transparency regarding impact, usage and other metrics, which are needed to demonstrate value.
- The titles published under some schemes are not always relevant to the teaching or research of the institution, and they have no input into those choices.
- Awareness of OA in general with researchers, and a lack of understanding around copyright implications.
- Inertia (*'It often comes down to prestige and prior relationships in monograph publishing and getting people to move to new models can be very difficult.'*)
- Transparency with regard to progress towards the funding targets.
- Pledge models do not always meet their target and unlock, and when they do the turnaround time for making titles OA can be sluggish.
- Discoverability can be a challenge (one librarian noted the challenges faced by small publishers in supplying metadata, *'so even if we invest in them, their OA content may not end up being well-used'*).
- Difficulties in ascertaining OA status (*'If a publisher releases both open access books as well as books in a closed access collection, there have been issues with knowing which books are open or which books we should have access to.'*)
- Schemes not being promoted widely (*'the burden of support falls on the same narrow pool of institutions'*).

- Lack of strategy with regard to EDI initiatives.
- With BPC models, commitment to payment is often required well in advance of payment, and funding in advance over multiple financial years can create challenges.

Return on investment

Where institutions actively support OA books financially, we asked how they evaluate the return on investment.

Many librarians reported that they had no means of doing so, either because the problem seemed intractable, or because they hadn't yet reached the stage where that was required. A few indicated that they did not feel the need to do so; support of OA aligned with their values, which was sufficient reason to continue.

For those attempting an evaluation, there was no consensus as to methods. Assessments fell into two camps: those undertaken before committing funds, and those carried out after publication.

When considering proposals, a number of factors were considered (the emphasis on each varied across respondents):

- Cost, sometimes evaluated as a cost per book.
- Where access to backlist is offered, the relevance of those titles to the university curriculum (in some cases measured by appearance on reading lists) and areas of research, and the number of titles.
- Where available, usage data on the backlist titles offered and on previous packages supported.
- Whether the institution's authors are represented in the books supported by the programme.
- Sustainability, openness, transparency and equity.
- Availability of good metadata.

For assessment after the fact, a number of librarians reported that usage data was a factor (at the same time, most acknowledged the problems inherent in such data). Other assessment criteria included:

- Feedback from faculties.
- Inclusion of items on reading lists.
- Number of outputs produced with authors from the institution.
- Where there are institutional authors, feedback from them on the publisher's processes.
- Quality assessment of supported content.

Many libraries reported that a lack of funds (both overall, and in terms of a lack of specific budget for OA) was the prime consideration in considering whether to support OA initiatives. Other general issues included:

- Getting admin buy-in and dealing with complex and sometimes protracted financial processes and regulations.
- The difficulty of maintaining recurrent spend (which is different from buying monographs: a one-off spend).
- The challenges of negotiating a confusing landscape with many competing models.
- A lack of clarity regarding VAT, and the challenge of increased exposure to VAT for publishing services.

Several respondents were keen to support smaller publishers.

Acquiring and using OA books

67 libraries answered a question about which platforms they used to learn about individual monographs. There was no consistent approach, and 16 librarians noted that they didn't really have a system. 18 found publisher mailings helpful, although only a couple looked at publisher websites. Other sources were recommendations from faculty (8), aggregator platforms (6), DOAB (14), EBSCO (5), Jisc (6), and various Listservs (4). A scattering of others (including ALMA Community Zone) were mentioned only a few times.

The consensus was that locating titles in the first place was a much larger problem than making OA academic books discoverable by users. With regard to the latter, the general feeling was that it was relatively straightforward to include titles (or collections of titles) in their usual systems (Primo, OCLC Collection Manager, etc.), provided that appropriate metadata was available. The problem is that the metadata is often lacking. A number of librarians commented that MARC records were essential.

Not all librarians agreed on the issues. One commented:

'The number of different discovery directories making OA content available creates overwhelming numbers of resources, and can lead to substantial duplication of targets within the discovery layer, for example one title might be being made available on 6 or 7 different aggregated OA sites, which looks messy and can be confusing on Primo.'

Meanwhile, one of their colleagues argued for the opposite:

'The volume of OA academic book publishing is easily high enough that we could never spare the resources to individual catalogue all titles of interest. We therefore want publishers to expose all of their title metadata through as many means as possible (e.g. DOAB, OAPEN, discovery layers) to give their titles a reasonable chance of being discovered alongside non-OA content.'

We asked whether libraries used separate acquisition channels for print and ebooks. About 80% used the same channels in general, while 20% used separate channels. In a few cases, while most purchases used the same channels, there were exceptions for certain print or ebook acquisitions. For example, a couple of libraries used the same channel for both but had an entirely different workflow for packages.

69% of libraries confirmed that they would usually acquire an ebook or a print version of a title, but not both. 24% said that they often acquired both, as they served different needs, and 7% stated that there was no link between the separate acquisition streams. Many noted that this was not a hard and fast rule. Both print and ebooks were often purchased for essential texts on reading lists.

Only 15% of librarians confirmed that the existence of an OA version of a title would have no bearing on print acquisitions. Nearly half (46%) would not buy print if an OA version were available, and a further 38% said that it would make a print purchase less likely. Various caveats were made: print is sometimes required for accessibility reasons; titles on reading lists were more likely to be acquired in print; and print would be purchased if specifically asked for by faculty. When print is purchased, 90% of respondents stated that the existence of an OA version would make no difference to the choice of paperback or hardback. Only 10% said that it would be a consideration.

We asked, 'Do you buy enhanced e-editions of titles if a "flat" OA version exists (e.g. a format such as PDF with no added functionality)?' 60% of respondents said that they would be less likely to buy the enhanced edition, with 40% stating that it would make no difference.

Only 4% of librarians said that they routinely visit individual publisher websites to acquire OA academic books. A further 50% would do so in response to specific user requests that could not be fulfilled through usual channels, and the remaining 46% did not look at publisher sites at all.

We asked how important it was that a title appeared on a class reading list in order to be selected for acquisition. The average score was 6 on a 10-point scale, but as can be seen in Figure 7 the distribution of answers clusters at both ends, with some libraries not considering it at all important while well over half regard it as very important.

Figure 7 Importance of appearing on reading lists.

Hybrid titles

With hybrid titles we were interested to know whether libraries could easily discover which chapters are OA. 38 said they couldn't, 9 said they could, and a further 9 felt that it depended on the publisher and their platform. One librarian commented:

'It's easier to exclude hybrid titles from our full text holdings than deal with the confusion it causes.'

and another said:

'It is likely the only time we would identify an individual chapter was open access would be if the specific chapter was requested for adding to a reading list; and in such instances we would often purchase the entire book as it would be uncommon for the chapter to only be read in isolation and not result in a request

for the book as a whole. There is an added complication in that users of hybrid content are often confused as to why other parts of the book are not accessible, and this generates both user-dissatisfaction and added admin costs in checking and responding to queries (or purchasing content or sourcing other chapters from other sources).'

Making OA chapters discoverable by users, if the library has not bought the entire book, is problematic. 44% felt that it was too complicated to be viable, and a further 46% said that it could only be done with some effort. Only 10% thought that it was relatively straightforward.

Opinion was split on the issue of whether increasing the number of OA chapters in hybrid books is actually worthwhile: 35% thought it was still worthwhile despite the discoverability problems, while 65% thought that it was not:

'Both because of the complexity and additional cost, but also because we would not want half a book available and not the rest.'

Help for libraries

We asked what resources would be helpful to support librarians in acquiring and promoting OA books. Popular suggestions included:

- A glossary of terms.
- A guide to different models for OA books.
- Effective tools to advocate for and promote OA monographs across the institution.
- Case studies and testimonials from authors who have published OA books.
- Practical advice on how to make OA titles and chapters discoverable in library systems.
- Advice on ways of measuring value for money.
- A checklist for how to assess quality and stability of OA platforms.
- A central place to find, browse and pledge/subscribe to OA books or packages.
- A centralized usage reporting tool allowing libraries to look at overall take-up as well as their own use of titles.

NB: The fact that some of these resources may exist already highlights the fact that it can be hard to find out what help is available or to evaluate its usefulness.

Advice for publishers

We asked what advice librarians would offer academic book publishers wishing to transition to OA and seeking library support. There were a number of common threads:

- Invest time in talking to libraries and really understanding decision-making processes around purchasing and discovery, library workflows and metadata needs, etc.
- Make costs transparent.
- Make any offers compelling in terms of content and price.
- Be clear about what works will be made OA, and how/when this will happen.
- Be realistic; most libraries are currently not in a position to financially support a lot of OA book publishing (particularly at smaller institutions).
- Avoid BPC models if possible.
- Good metadata is key.
- Explore Green OA models.
- Get your collections into Alma.
- Make sure you are included in DOAB.

- Make OA information easy to find on your website.
- Ensure any OA scheme is equitable for all authors and readers.
- Highlight the quality of your publishing processes and give evidence/examples of what you have published to help encourage author buy-in.
- Provide support for authors securing 3rd party copyright clearance.
- Meet WCAG accessibility guidelines.
- Keep a robust electronic preservation plan in place.

And finally:

'Be very careful and do your due diligence. Don't assume that just because your project is morally virtuous, it therefore must be financially sustainable. No publishing project can succeed at scale or in the long term without a viable business model, and if your business model is going to rely on library funds, make sure you have reason to believe that a critical mass of libraries' host institutions (which are the source of their funds) are on board with the goals of your project. Otherwise, it may seem to succeed in the short run and at small scale, but will be doomed in the long run and at large scale.'

Appendix 4 – 20 September 2024 Cross-Stakeholder Workshop

Introduction

Tahia Zaidi from UKRI welcomed participants and provided some context for the project. Alicia Wise provided an overview of the project and the next steps. She explained that the project team would use the inputs from the project to refine the report and toolkit contents.

Plenary discussion of draft OA Book Vision

Participants reviewed the vision; one said it is an aspiration, a target to aim for and largely unarguable.

However, it was noted that the word 'rewarded' may be ambiguous because the type of reward depends on who the stakeholder is. For researchers, it may be the acknowledgement and reach of their research, for publishers it may be revenue and greater partnership with institutions, etc.

It was pointed out that when talking about OA books being accessible and affordable we must be mindful that this includes the non-research communities as well as academic communities.

One participant asked if there is still a strong concern from scholars, librarians, and other stakeholders that OA publications are not quality-assured?

- Lorraine said that during the project she had heard this is still a concern for some, but perhaps not as much as there once was. She also mentioned that predatory publishers (who take money from authors and don't offer proper services) operate which damages trust.
- Another noted that prestige is very important for some authors, and they want established publishers they have heard of. This can make it difficult for new entrants who are doing innovative things to diversify the bibliosphere.
- Another said they sense perceptions about the quality of OA books have changed dramatically for the better in the last decade. But there are still pockets of concern. There is some regional variation here. More concerns about quality in the U.S. versus Europe.
- A participant noted that authors are less embedded in the Academy, perhaps because they've had more precarious career paths, may be less familiar with OA, and therefore have less trust in it.

Another participant asked what 'interoperable' means in this context. Lorraine explained it meant that along the supply chain and different systems, OA books are discoverable and accessible. So that they are discoverable by librarians who want to acquire them, and findable by their users.

It was pointed out that 'reusable' depends on which Creative Commons licence a book is published under.

Another participant asked, 'When the vision says, "preserved as part of our shared long-term cultural and intellectual heritage," who will do the preservation in this vision?'

- Lorraine pointed out that several trusted organizations provide publishers with an infrastructure for digital preservation, and national libraries also play a role.
- A participant noted that his hope is that the version of record is preserved, not only an unfinished version deposited in a repository.

When discussing 'sustainability', the term should apply to both libraries and publishers. It's important to be aware that a significant portion of publisher revenues comes from other countries. In some of these countries, open access is not a priority, so there is less demand for OA books. Therefore, one market supports OA books, while another market prefers to buy them.

Cross-stakeholder breakout groups

Participants discussed four questions in each of four groups:

- What information does a book publisher need, and when, to decide to publish a title OA using either a Collective Funding Model or BPC?
- What information does a library need, and when, to decide to financially support a title OA using either a Collective Funding Model or BPC?
- What relevant information is being provided (or not) at the crucial decision points and how?
- How might systems evolve to support more publishers to publish more OA books?

Report from Group 1

What information does a publisher need, and when, to decide whether to publish a title as OA using either a Collective Funding Model or a Book Processing Charge (BPC)?

From a publisher's perspective, gathering the necessary information for a BPC-based OA model is often complex. A key challenge lies in determining and agreeing upon the BPC itself, which may involve discussions with the funder and/or author. The amount can vary significantly depending on the length of the book and any specialized typesetting or formatting needs, which may increase costs.

Additionally, publishers need to identify the relevant funders and determine the appropriate recipient for invoicing. Importantly, the organization paying the invoice may differ from the funder. Publishers also require clarity regarding the funders' licensing requirements for OA publication, and they must ensure that the author approves publishing their work as OA.

For collective funding models, publishers need to confirm whether the funding target has been met, as this information does not always align with the book's publication timeline. If funding is incomplete, the book might not be published as OA, potentially causing it to drop out of the collective funding model. Once the funding is secured, the author's approval for OA publication is still necessary.

Furthermore, societies that work with publishing partners encounter additional challenges. Responsibilities between the society and the publisher can become unclear, leading to delays or confusion in decision-making as information is passed between them.

What information does a library need, and when, to decide to financially support an OA title using either a Collective Funding Model or BPC?

From the library's perspective, BPCs are often not feasible due to a lack of dedicated funds. However, libraries may have some budget available for collective funding models. For planning purposes, it is crucial for libraries to know which books will be included in such models before the start of the financial year when budget allocations are made.

A recent OCLC research project has focused on the discoverability of OA books, highlighting that libraries face challenges in locating OA titles within mixed collections. The trustworthiness of sources was a key theme in this research. Acquisition librarians often rely on subject librarians' recommendations, and the reputation of the publisher plays a significant role in decision-making. If a publisher is unfamiliar, there may be hesitation in supporting their titles. The relevance of a book to local research priorities, especially those related to a country's own academic output, is also a critical factor.

Another issue is the poor quality of metadata provided for some books. Even when metadata is available, various systems may selectively display information, including whether a book is OA, making it harder for libraries to identify and promote OA titles.

What relevant information is provided (or not) at crucial decision points, and how?

For publishers, managing the timing of funding (for BPCs) is a persistent challenge. There is often a lack of clarity regarding the funding criteria and deadlines. If a book experiences delays—such as an extended peer review process or a slower-than-expected delivery—publishers may miss funding windows. This uncertainty complicates planning and can strain the relationship with the author.

In some cases, societies have committed BPC waivers for certain books in advance, but delivery delays could cause the waiver to expire, forcing the book to lose its chance at OA publication. For example, UKRI has a seven-year timeframe for OA publication but tries to remain flexible, though this is difficult given the many variables involved.

How might systems evolve to support more publishers in publishing OA books?

It was noted that 'flipping' books to OA after publication can erode library trust, particularly when metadata about the OA version is not linked to the paid version. This can lead to confusion among librarians, who may perceive the publisher's actions as misleading, even when this is due to outdated or incomplete information.

A shared infrastructure could help publishers scale up their OA offerings more efficiently. However, there remains uncertainty around how such a system would be funded, highlighting the need for collaborative solutions.

[Report from Group 2](#)

What information does a library need to decide to fund OA?

- Collection building, relevant content: does the title fit the collection, the need of faculty? In other words: justify the use of resources
 - Why to prioritize instead of other budget requests
 - Usage statistics
 - Is other funding (outside the library) available?
- How to present the funding call to libraries:

- Make sure there is an alignment with the collection
- Be clear about the investment needed
- A rolling fund for OA? This is not a possibility for all libraries.

When should this information be made available to libraries?

- When libraries want to fund authors from their own institution: early knowledge of upcoming titles is needed. The supply chain should be able to provide forewarning.

What relevant information is provided (or not) at crucial decision points, and how?

- The current collective UKRI funding does not work for specialized publishers. On top of that: There are different requirements per funding scheme.
 - Requirement for UKRI-funded researchers? Not always possible
- The group discussed the information needs of libraries:
 - When using collective models it is important to identify an organization's 'own' authors. To enable this, author/employer/funder identifiers are needed and should be made available.
 - Future publishing data is not available although this would be highly desirable
 - Licence information should be available in bulk, not just at the book level but also at the chapter level
 - There are different workflows for open access books vs closed access books: the extra monitoring for OA is a burden for libraries
 - Usage: COUNTER R5 is important
- There is a tension between funding requirements: collective funding is conditional, which makes it complicated
- Current title management systems used by publishers can't cope well with funding schemes.
 - Using Thoth scaled up as a solution? Many publishers have their own systems, so this would not work for all.
- At the end of the session, the following remarks were made:
 - Involve stakeholders from different countries (worldwide), not just UK/Europe
 - Differentiate between the organization that has provided the research funding and the organization that has provided the OA publishing funding.

In summary:

- Differences in funders lead to different constraints.
- Libraries find it difficult to identify 'own' authors.
- Book data collection by publishers is less mature compared to journals.

A librarian noted that they do not engage with BPCs because they are not sustainable or affordable for them. A similar comment from another librarian who noted that unless there is external funding they are not considering paying individual BPCs.

Models that are handled through Jisc were highlighted as being very convenient and accessible, as a lot of the legwork has been done centrally by Jisc. It would be great if more smaller publishers could be integrated into this or some similar mechanism.

A participant said that it would be nice if funding could be spread out more broadly and predictably. It is now often unclear which titles will be unlocked, since it is so uncertain how many libraries will end up joining the schemes within specific timeframes.

Maximum transparency is needed. It would be helpful if Jisc could make available information about how far a proposal has been funded.

Libraries often have some remaining funds at the end of the year, which are often allocated to support collective funding models. However, this amount is insufficient or unsuitable for funding expensive BPCs.

Where is the money for an OA books fund going to come from? It can't be saved by ceasing to do some other activity. It is uncertain how it will work out for libraries that are often under budget cuts.

BPCs are hard to implement equitably, to treat all potential authors of an institution equally in terms of availability and eligibility for such funding. Librarians are unwilling to be put in the position of choosing which of their authors can be funded.

It is helpful when publishers make direct connections with librarians. However, there is clearly a problem of scalability. When publishers or managers of collective funding models do outreach, it is helpful if they can be customized to the specific institution, mentioning books already published through the publisher/programme to demonstrate the immediate relevance/utility.

Currently, it is only easy to enable OA book publishing for UKRI-funded researchers, since there is \$3m in ring-fenced funding available to support implementation of the policy. If research funders want OA book publishing to happen, they need to provide funds.

Standardized information about costs, etc. would be useful but difficult for small-scale/small-volume publishers and university presses.

Scalability is a problem. One librarian reported supporting a couple of small-scale projects, but many more are being offered, including by the big publishers who offer much the same deals.

An open dashboard showing what projects currently need support would be helpful.

[Report from Group 4](#)

What information does a book publisher need and when?

The discussion focussed on unconditional OA revenue models. Conditional models lead to retrospective flipping to OA of books already published. As explained in the project report, there are many challenges for both libraries and publishers of conditional models,

The group discussed and agreed that all OA book publishers currently use multiple revenue streams. For example, one explained that he uses a blend of income from a library membership model, BPCs where authors have grant income, and print sales.

The way the question is worded suggests that the publisher makes the decision to publish OA at the title level, and this often isn't the case. More often the decision is made at the collection or list level, and some models work best when the publisher has taken the decision at the whole-publisher level.

It is difficult for a publisher to predict whether a book will be successful. Publishers currently take all the risks, and sometimes it works and sometimes it doesn't. So, in practice, the revenue from some books subsidizes other books, and always has done.

A publisher reported that initially they needed to make a leap of faith to embrace OA publishing, and they started by subsidizing the costs of their first OA titles, not confident where the money for these would come from. In practice the money did come, and it came from selling print.

We dug into the question of ways to decrease the need to take a blind leap of faith:

- If OA funding is available, then publishers in the group initially said they would find it very helpful to know this at any time until the book is published. (After this, all the problems with retrospective flipping kick in.)
- It's even more helpful to know much earlier than the point of publication, particularly for titles that will be in subject collections, as these collections are pre-sold and priced a year in advance. Publishers were particularly sensitive to potential accusations of double-dipping if they sold a book in a collection that was then published OA. It was agreed that it is very important not to sell books published OA.
- Ideally collections would be marketed with complete information about titles and whether any of these are OA, but a much greater lead-in time would be needed for this to happen. Instead, collections are often sold without any title information at all, or sometimes indicating the number of titles only. This gives intermediaries/publishers a bit of room for flexibility when putting together the collection.
- Intermediaries find collection list building a very delicate and fragile process. Publishers are asked to submit titles a year in advance, but many things can happen. For example, authors might deliver the book late or with a somewhat different focus than anticipated.
- Intermediaries reported that they have not yet attempted cross-publisher list building because they anticipate this would be even more challenging.
- Jisc has piloted a 6-month funding window for lists of about 10 titles. These tend to be whichever are the next 10 titles in the publisher's queue. Libraries would prefer to pledge for specific subjects or titles, but it isn't possible to do this at present.

What information does a library need and when?

- It is difficult for libraries to identify relevant titles to fund (e.g. those that acknowledge UKRI funding where they can tap into OA publishing funds). It would be helpful if publishers could give the relevant library or libraries a heads-up as soon as they know they have an author who might be eligible for institutional or funder support. Too often libraries only end up learning of such books by accident.
- When an author has paid a BPC, the library often isn't informed by either the author or the publisher. This means the library can't keep track of demand for

OA book publishing. The key message to publishers is: please get in touch with the relevant library or libraries asap when you are contemplating publishing a book by an academic author.

- OA switchboard book pilot will help book publishers communicate this information to libraries.
- It is also essential for publishers to flag future OA books in Ebook Central and GOBI, but this process is very manual at present.
- Use of previous collections produced by a publisher helps libraries to establish their track record, and would be factored into decision making about who/what to support. Libraries also use relevance of author/funding source to their institution/budget, relevance of the subject areas, and appearance of the title on local reading lists.
- Libraries can helpfully add instructions to their approval plans that they would like to prioritize purchases from publishers that make a digital version available OA, and they could even specify a preference to support smaller and specialist publishers to aid their transition. Approval plans lead to pre-orders and early sales for publishers.
- Many of the libraries represented on the call did not have the luxury of purchasing plans, of course, and must use 'whatever change we can find down the back of our sofas' to support OA book publishing.
- Library budgets for reading need to be repurposed to support a full transition to OA book publishing and may need to think more broadly about the value of OA for their readers.
- How do academic authors or readers know which OA book publishing scheme or schemes their library supports?
- Consortia struggle to get awareness/visibility of what small publishers are doing. In the journal transition Jisc appointed a full-time member of staff to work with smaller and specialist journal publishers for a year, and this was tremendously helpful.
- Could national consortia (or, aspirationally, a global coalition of library consortia) pool library resources/bandwidth to support more small and specialist book publishers to publish OA?

How might systems evolve to better support smaller and specialist publishers?

- Raise awareness of the Open Book Collective, which is a platform for bringing libraries and publishers together. For this model to scale up, the participation of libraries and publishers needs to grow at about the same rate.
- Sweden uses a tool called Diva for pre-allocating money from universities to fund the printing and dissemination of theses and dissertations. Here's an example: https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/resultList.jsf?dswid=-1386&language=en&searchType=SIMPLE&query=Abeni+Wickham&af=%5B%5D&aq=%5B%5B%5D%5D&aq2=%5B%5B%5D%5D&aqe=%5B%5D&noOfRows=50&sortOrder=author_sort_asc&sortOrder2=title_sort_asc&onlyFullText=false&sf=all. Scroll down and there is a link to the publisher's site-> the Uni

LIU: <https://liu.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A848329&dswid=-1835>.

Additional input received by email immediately after the event

- Various initiatives are being generously funded by UKRI (through Research England) that have been explicitly designed to address some of the issues identified in this report to support small and medium-sized publishers in OA book production, distribution and non-BPC financing. This work is being done by COPIM. Also see <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/building-assessment-criteria-for-collection-development-policies-a-community-resource/release/1>
- We [a library] need to know about any funding mentioned in monographs or book chapters so that we can determine how to support open access for these titles, whether through article processing charges (APCs) or collective funding models. Our decision-making regarding collective funding models is not solely based on this information. While we already support various collective funding models through institutional funding, having information about funding can help us identify where we might be able to utilize UKRI funds. Once we are reimbursed by UKRI, we can reinvest that money in other schemes. Our participation in these schemes does not rely on one of our authors directly benefiting. However, being able to demonstrate that direct benefit does make things easier. When making these kinds of investments, our finance team often asks specifically how the investment will benefit the University. Senior research leaders would prefer to invest in APCs to publish one of our authors' work open access rather than support open access publishing for authors at other institutions. The Library takes a more principled approach and is eager to support the development of a more open, equitable monograph publishing ecosystem. While we have been allowed to continue doing this, if we were ever required to make savings, it seems likely that these collective funding models would be high on the list of investments to be cut first.
- One other thing to add is around transparency. I [a librarian] think this is a really valuable aspect of the vision statement, and I'd like to see publishers being more transparent about the publication process for their open access monographs. Routledge do a fairly good job of this on their website (<https://www.routledge.com/our-products/open-access-books/publishing-oa-books>). With most other publishers we deal with, this is much more murky! We often have no idea:
 - Whether OA is possible
 - How much a BPC will cost
 - At what point we'll be required to pay an invoice
 - When the book will be made OA – on publication? After a delay?

That being said, we often find that the people working for the publishers don't really know their processes either. We've arranged multiple OA books with one large university press and each time the process has been totally different. All of this makes it quite difficult to advise authors too. So a) more information, publicly available and b) more consistency in processes would make life much easier for us.

Appendix 5 – Case study: White Horse Press

The Publisher: **The White Horse Press** is an independent academic publisher specializing in environmental humanities and social sciences.

Introduction

Founded 35 years ago, The White Horse Press is a family-run, independent publisher with no shareholders. Its mission is to publish books and journals on environment and society, with particular specialisms in environmental history, environmental ethics, climate history, interdisciplinary plant studies, and nomadic societies.

The press is highly specialized and has no trade sales.

The press publishes 5–6 books per year, with 25% of sales being digital. Approximately 23% of authors are from the UK, around 25% are from Europe, 25% are from the USA, and the remainder are from the rest of the world (ROW). Sales are 90% to libraries and 10% to consumers.

Their books are not hugely lucrative. They publish to support their field and build author relationships, aiming to break even on books, covering costs and contributing to overheads.

Drivers for OA

The White Horse Press is committed to reducing and removing barriers to access for the material it publishes.

Its journals have offered a green option since 2007.

Two years ago, The White Horse Press began OA publishing for three main reasons:

1. OA encourages wider dissemination and diversifies citations. This is good in itself, and also fits with the company's mission of publishing on environmental issues. The more widely the publications are read and cited, the greater contribution they may make towards positive environmental outcomes.
2. Anticipating a transition to OA and not wanting to join late after a tipping point.
3. To lower financial risk. With paywalled models, it is uncertain if the costs of producing the first copy will be recovered. With OA models, upfront fees cover the cost of producing the book and any print sales provide additional revenue.

The White Horse Press is working hard to become a fully OA publisher, and this ambition includes flipping all back book publications to OA under CC BY licences. So far, 13 of the 58 backlist books are now OA. The priority is to flip books authored by Early Career Researchers (ECRs), independent researchers, and scholars from the Global South.

Their authors, with few exceptions, are very positive about OA. Those who are reluctant to have their books published in OA usually have low awareness of what it means and feel cautious about giving something away.

Revenue models

Some OA models The White Horse Press tried did not work for them.

For instance, with journals they initially tried a transformative agreement but later switched to a subscribe-to-open model which has proven more successful and attracted a few more subscribers. Libraries have the option to subscribe to individual journals or a collection of five journals. Authors do not have to pay APCs for fully OA titles and those at subscribing institutions receive a discount on APCs in the one hybrid journal. The White Horse Press partnered with Liverpool University Press for their journals to take advantage of additional capacity and skills.

For books and edited collections, they started with BPCs and still use this model if authors have funding. However, as a principle, the White Horse Press prefers not to charge BPCs. When a book is submitted and accepted, authors are asked if they would like their book or chapter published OA. If not, they can choose to pay to flip to OA later. BPCs vary according to the complexity of the work, but indicative costs are £8,000 for up to 80,000 words or £9,000 for up to 100,000 words. These charges include copyediting and the provision of an index.

The White Horse Press proactively participates in initiatives including:

Knowledge Unlatched (KU): So far enabling three backlist books to be converted to OA.

Open Book Collective: This aggregates small presses and enables libraries to support a single press or a collection of books with customizable subscription packages. The benefit of participation is access to a helpful technical infrastructure and scale, as the Press does not have capacity to deal with many libraries and libraries cannot deal with many independent publishers.

Print sales

In all cases, a print version of a book is available for purchase and simultaneously digital publication is made available OA. The White Horse Press has not yet analysed the impact of OA on print sales. Their impression is that sales have not decreased, but they are aware that this could change in the longer term. The Press normally only produces paperback editions of its OA books, assuming that libraries will not buy hardback editions if there is an OA digital version.

Supply chain and metadata

The books are available on JSTOR, OAPEN, and the Open Research Library (ORL). The Thoth project holds White Horse Press metadata in its database.

The White Horse Press has seen that OA increases the usage of their books. When titles have flipped to OA, usage increases. Through Knowledge Unlatched, one book's usage increased tenfold.

Appendix 6 – Case study: University of London Press

The Publisher: **The University of London Press is part of the School of Advanced Study at the University of London, based at Senate House.**

Introduction

The University of London Press is an integral part of the School of Advanced Study at the University of London, which receives special funding from Research England to promote and facilitate humanities research. Institutional support for the Press from this funding primarily covers staffing costs for a small team and the publishing costs of 20–25 books each year in their 'core' OA book series without author charges. These 'core' OA series support the School's strategy to advance the humanities through books which open new research agendas and methodological approaches, explore the future of humanities disciplines, and advocate for the humanities. Around 85% of their funding covers staffing and publishing costs, with the Press seeking to diversify income streams to support their sustainability and growth through its participation in new collective funding models.

The Press also receives limited income from the print sales of books, which is reinvested into its publishing programme, its broader advocacy work for humanities disciplines, and training for humanities researchers. The Press is working to create ePub versions of its backlist, which will be sold at the lowest print price. While print sales are declining, having digital versions available is important. Revenue from ebooks will be a small portion of their total funding.

Drivers for OA

The University of London Press has a long publishing history and a commitment to supporting researchers. Their mission is to 'open up humanities research'. They are a non-profit, predominantly OA, university press and an expert and creative publishing partner for the authors and organizations they work with. The proven benefits of OA publishing in making important ideas available to a more diverse and global readership are particularly critical for humanities research, expanding collective understanding of human cultures, societies, histories, and languages. As a passionate advocate for the humanities, the Press wants its publications to have a global audience and to open up debate. OA is critical to their mission.

The University of London Press is predominantly OA. Some books, such as those with a significant number of images, cannot be fully OA due to third-party rights concerns. The Press also does not want to exclude authors who are still hesitant about OA, and so they ensure space in the publishing programme for those authors and projects where OA is not feasible for different reasons.

Revenue models

Support through the School of Advanced Study covers the publishing costs of 20–25 books each year in the Press's 'core' OA series, the majority of which are OA without requiring authors to pay any fees. External funding comes from various sources (see below) with different durations, ranging from one to three years. Keeping track of these commitments and ensuring correct financial processing can be complex and resource intensive for a small team.

For books published outside their 'core' OA series, or where authors have access to funding, the Press charges authors a BPC of £6,000 plus VAT. Authors at SAS or federal member institutions within the University of London receive a 25% discount. Costs depend on word length:

- Up to 100,000 words: £6,000 plus VAT.
- Short form (20-50,000 words): £4,500 plus VAT.

The Press's institutional funding can also be used for a small number of books that directly relate to the School's mission to advance humanities research outside their 'core' OA series. This includes books advocating for the humanities, those which explore the future of humanities disciplines, and those offering innovative models for publishing research.

The University of London Press sees real value in collective funding models, such as the Open Book Collective which offers libraries a pick-and-mix model where libraries that specialize in arts and humanities can filter for relevant publishers and programs. The more publishers that are involved the better, creating a larger-scale initiative without requiring individual presses to expand their operations significantly. One challenge is that the UKRI Open Access funding does not currently align well with these consortial funding models, making it difficult to guarantee support for UKRI-funded authors within these schemes.

They proactively participate in initiatives including:

- **Jisc's Open Access Community Framework (OACF):** Gained support from 10 UK institutional libraries for the New Historical Perspectives series, and support (to date) from 6 UK libraries for new books on human rights and social justice.
- **Open Book Collective:** Joined at the start of 2024, allowing libraries to support their work through various packages. Aggregates small presses into a unit, allowing libraries to support a single press or a 'package' of publishers. This platform can usefully enhance library outreach and scale up the impact, without requiring individual presses to scale up on their own. The University of London Press have seen significant support coming through from libraries since January 2024 through this promising model, and this is already supporting the Press to grow and enhance their open access publishing programme and wider activity.
- **Knowledge Unlatched (KU):** Usually enables about one book a year to be published OA.

Print sales

The Press receives limited and declining income from the print sales of books (including print sales of OA books). Operating as both a traditional print publisher and an OA publisher requires distinct strategies and practices. Prioritizing between developing OA platform dissemination and maintaining the (closed) print backlist can be a constant challenge with a limited team and funding.

Supply chain and metadata

Lacking a dedicated institutional sales team, the Press relies on a marketing person using social media and other activities for outreach and two distributors for global distribution of print titles.

Limited capacity and lack of the specific skills required to reach libraries effectively necessitate reliance on platforms like JSTOR and OAPEN.

The press is currently creating EPUBs of backlist titles which will be sold via one of their distributors.

The Press is also working with Thoth, a non-profit open metadata management and dissemination platform for OA books, to improve visibility and dissemination. A pilot with Thoth is underway to evaluate its costs and benefits, and the Press anticipates real value in this scalable new infrastructure supporting OA book publishing.

Managing and representing usage data coming from various digital platforms manually has been challenging.

In conclusion, the University of London Press is seeing real benefits in publishing OA books which have increased global readership in key regions, and enabled the Press to experiment and innovate with new publishing models for humanities research and win prestigious prizes.

Appendix 7 – Case study: Berghahn Books

The Publisher: **Berghahn Books** is an independent publisher of scholarly books and journals in the humanities and social sciences.

Introduction

Established 30 years ago, Berghahn Books is a family-run academic press that releases over 125 new book titles and 60 paperback editions annually, alongside a portfolio of journals. Berghahn has embraced OA publishing as an effective means to enhance the dissemination of its publications to address pressing societal needs.

Berghahn's OA journey began in 2016 as an early participant in the Knowledge Unlatched (KU) Select collections and the Press has continued to work with KU each year since to secure OA funding for selected titles (it has funded 60 OA titles to date this way). Additional titles are published OA each year with the assistance of institutional funding for those authors (48 titles in total so far). However, the Press has always been mindful of the limitations of author-pay approaches, especially for its core fields in the social sciences and humanities where funding resources are sparse. Berghahn has therefore worked to promote consortial funding models that pool library funding to collectively support OA publication. Their first initiative to do so, with outreach help from KU, is the Migration and Development collection, with titles that focus on international migration, movement, and the socio-economic and environmental impacts of these phenomena, aligning with global policy relevance. This initiative (detailed below) has raised enough funds to publish 35 OA titles between 2021 and 2026.

Drivers for OA

- Building trust, fostering communication, and prioritizing the needs of authors and research communities are key principles.
- Titles are chosen for OA based on their alignment with sustainability goals, author support, and potential societal impact.
- By supporting faculty and expanding their access to OA publishing, Berghahn fosters a more collaborative and supportive research environment using models that best meet the needs of their authors.

Opportunities

Unlike larger publishers, Berghahn's strategy involves direct, more personalized engagement with libraries, faculty, editors, and authors. The Press recognizes that libraries and librarians are at the heart of the international academic communities they publish for and are key to the access to and engagement with their publications. This grassroots approach therefore fosters a deeper understanding of ongoing institutional needs and interests, creating stronger, more authentic relationships.

As a smaller press that prioritizes a more relational approach to its publishing programme, Berghahn can emphasize how OA funds are reinvested into its publishing programme, highlighting areas like production quality, peer review rigour, and its active role in disseminating the contributions of its authors more widely. These multifaceted commitments can demonstrate the publisher's value to the scholarly community.

Challenges

- Navigating Institutional Policies: Authors often face challenges when caught between institutional policies regarding OA publishing and the long-term sustainability of publishers they value. Publishers need to be more engaged in discussions with universities to understand the specific issues and provide tailored support to authors navigating these policies.
- Creative Commons (CC) BY without ND: Potential risks and unintended consequences are associated with CC licences that are too broad and limit authorial control over their own works, particularly in sensitive and contentious fields that can lead to reputable scholarly works appearing alongside pseudo-scientific or extremist content. This juxtaposition could potentially damage scholars' reputations and undermine their work's credibility.
- CC BY without NC: For consortial funding models that pool library funds, ensuring supplemental forms of income can help lower the thresholds needed and contribute to more publications securing the OA funding with greater stability and lower barriers for all stakeholders.
- Green OA attributed to a Creative Commons (CC) without an embargo: Authors need to be provided with more information about the implications of rights retention strategies and why certain publishers may require an embargo period, especially for niche subject areas that are most often championed by the smaller – and therefore most vulnerable – publishers.

Revenue models

As a reputable publisher in its fields, the Press finds it can proactively participate in initiatives that leverage the purchasing power of libraries via targeted subject collections. This approach provides institutions with revenue incentives for purchasing those titles their faculty value from a Publisher they trust, all while delivering a possible path to OA for the titles in that collection. The Berghahn Open Migration and Development Studies initiative is one such example.

This initiative launched in 2021 and offers libraries a collection of 20 titles per year (60 across a 3-year cycle) with funds pooled towards supporting the OA publication for as many of those titles as possible. Libraries receive access to all those titles. During its first three-year cycle (2021-2023), the initiative secured OA for 15 titles. Now entering its second cycle (2024-2026), the collection is already well ahead of its first cycle and has already secured OA funding for another 20 titles. This is thanks to the ongoing

support of libraries from the first cycle alongside new libraries signing on. Most libraries are signing up for 3-year cycles, which provides longer-term stability for initiative and enables more effective list planning and title preparation. The Press hopes to expand this initiative to other subjects that seek to make similar impacts.

Where institutional or funder mandates fall outside the purview of its consortial funding initiatives, Berghahn also offers single title Book Publishing Charges (BPC) options:

- Per Chapter: Up to \$2,000
- Full Volume: Up to \$15,000

Supply chain and metadata

Berghahn hosts its OA titles on its own website as well as distributing the files to the main ebook platforms that distribute its standard ebook content. Integrating OA titles into platforms such as JSTOR ensures those titles are in the academic ecosystem and can be accessed by researchers alongside non-OA titles in their subject areas.

Berghahn utilizes usage data and author publication benefits to refine marketing efforts and identify libraries that actively use and support their collections as part of renewal and future new funding campaigns. Authors, particularly those contributing institutional BPCs, are increasingly interested in usage data to demonstrate the global impact of their research back to their funders. Providing visually compelling usage data statements, similar to traditional royalty reports, can enhance transparency and accountability while also illustrating the benefits of OA to authors who may initially be sceptical. There remain hurdles: the lack of standards around usage statistic reporting and the challenges of collecting widely dispersed data are the reason Berghahn is encouraged by multi-stakeholder industry initiatives, such as OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAeBUDT), which are keen to deliver solutions for publishers of all sizes, including smaller ones like Berghahn.

Appendix 8 – Background study and references

During the last decade there has been a wealth of literature written on the subject of OA books and associated revenue models. Rather than summarizing each contribution to the literature individually and in chronological order, we have grouped contributions to produce a practical, usable overview that we hope will be useful to learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers.

Drivers for OA book publishing

It is important to point out that authors, funders, libraries, and publishers are all important stakeholders shaping the pace and shape of the OA transition. Helpfully there is literature available that will enable you take a deep dive into the perspectives of stakeholders who may be less familiar to readers, including the author perspective (Collins Milloy & Stone 2015), the funder perspective (Ferwerda, Snijder, Arpagaus et al 2018), the library perspective (Farrell et al. 2021, Brundy et al. 2023), and the publisher perspective (Shaw, Phillips, & Gutiérrez 2023).

Whatever OA approaches are adopted need to take these perspectives into account. Fulfilling the needs of a subset of actors is unlikely to lead to a successful and sustainable solution.

Mandates

Funders or institutions may have OA policies requiring or encouraging authors to make their books or chapters openly accessible either immediately through the published version (i.e. Gold OA) and/or by self-archiving or depositing a version of the manuscript in an OA repository (i.e. Green OA).

The infrastructure for discovering the existence and details of OA policies for books and book chapters is still in its infancy. The Jisc Open Policy Finder tool has evolved to include an OA for Books tool⁹. Explaining these policies to authors, and ways in which a publisher can facilitate compliance, is a new responsibility for OA book publishers. Springer Nature is one example of a publisher that provides very clear information¹⁰.

European countries have been among pioneers for OA book publishing, where the UK is among the leaders and pathfinders in the transition to OA book publishing. The UK book landscape has been shaped by three drivers: 1) an emerging national-level policy framework, 2) a strong global publishing industry which is increasingly interested in OA publishing, and 3) experimentation by academics and institutional libraries and consortia (Ferwerda, Pinter, & Stern 2017).

It is close to a decade since Professor Geoffrey Crossick prepared the foundational review 'Monographs and open access' for the Higher Education Funding Council for England (Crossick 2015; Crossick 2016). Universities UK's Open Access and Monographs Group collected key facts concerning research on OA books from the perspective of UK higher education institutions (2019). UKRI introduced an OA mandate for monographs, book chapters, or edited collections for works published after 1 January 2024¹¹. The UK debate is now around the details of enabling more OA book publishing by authors and institutions, and when and how to extend an OA book publishing mandate to the REF.

⁹ <https://openpolicyfinder.jisc.ac.uk/oa-books>

¹⁰ <https://www.springernature.com/gp/open-research/funding/oa-policy-faqs-for-books-and-chapters>

¹¹ <https://www.ukri.org/manage-your-award/publishing-your-research-findings/making-your-monograph-book-chapter-or-edited-collection-open-access/>

Other funders and other parts of the world are also undertaking this journey:

- The Wellcome Trust has an OA policy for books published by its grant recipients, and permits authors of books more flexibility than authors of journal chapters in relation to embargoes and choice of open licence¹².
- The European Commission is a strong champion of OA and currently requires that books published as a result of its research funding are published OA. NWO in the Netherlands, another strong OA champion, has a special fund that authors can apply to for funding to publish a book OA¹³. A review of 14 European countries (Morka Gatti 2021) suggests funding for OA book publishing is rather rare. Only four of the countries (i.e. Germany, the Netherlands, Finland, and Norway) have dedicated OA book funds, some on the national level and others at the institutional or funder level. In the other ten countries included in the review, OA book publishing was most commonly funded through the inclusion of costs in grant proposals and with an amount of grant money allocated for OA publication fees. There are also a few examples of OA book publishing initiatives being partially subsidized by the national funders (e.g. OA books from the Faculty of Arts at the University of Ljubljana, Slovenia, and the Kallipos+ project in Greece).
- The National Endowment for the Humanities in the US is developing a public access policy some 10 years after federal science funders in the US did; however, this will apply only to journal outputs and not books. NEH does encourage wider dissemination, and it also provides small grants to enable scholars to open their books¹⁴.

It is clear these mandates will expand in number and scope. The Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area (PALOMERA) project, which is funded by the European Commission, has already collected over 200 OA book policies. Each is analysed in detail to identify good practices, current challenges, and bottlenecks. Most of the data collected is already available through the PALOMERA Knowledge Base¹⁵.

Authors

Particularly in the humanities and social sciences, book publishing is fundamental to the system of promotion and tenure. These subjects are traditionally less well funded than STEM subjects, and there is an extended lifecycle for published content (Suber 2017). Given this context, it is perhaps unsurprising that while authors in these fields sometimes embrace OA, many others are apprehensive.

In a survey of Springer Nature book authors, 80% of whom at that time had not yet published an OA book, SSH authors expressed concern and deemed certain types of reuse to be unacceptable. 51% were concerned about non-translation modifications and 54% were concerned about commercial reuse (Pyne, Emery et al 2019). 83% of non-OA book authors and 73% of OA book authors agreed or strongly agreed that having a print edition was important.

The University of Michigan Press conducted a broad author survey as well as editor, author, and librarian interviews to understand OA within different research fields (Frankl 2023). Funding was seen as the major obstacle for increased OA publishing among the majority of respondents. The main reservations authors had towards publishing their work OA were 'Disagree with pay to publish' (i.e. Book Processing Charges) with 56%

¹² <https://wellcome.org/grant-funding/guidance/open-access-guidance/open-access-policy>

¹³ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/calls/open-access-books>

¹⁴ <https://www.neh.gov/publicaccess>

¹⁵ <https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org/home>

selecting this option, and 'Could not afford fees' selected by 36% of respondents. Respondents also signalled that OA was increasingly common and accepted, and expected it to grow over the next 10 years. A useful output from this project is its OA Culture Framework, which provides a set of questions any publisher can use to consult with authors and editors.

Readers

Reaching the intended readers, and expanding the potential pool of readers, is a fundamental driver for successful OA.

Having OA books available with open licences, even the more restrictive creative commons ones, facilitates the inclusion of the content in intermediary services and platforms which likely increases the number of downloads of the content (Snijder 2015). Neylon, Ozaygen, Montgomery et al (2021) conducted a study on SpringerNature books to explore how OA books were accessed differently on the SpringerLink platform compared to a broad stratified sample of the publisher's non-OA books. All metrics were strongly in favour of the OA book sample, providing 'higher geographic diversity of usage, higher numbers of downloads and more citations for open access books across all strata'. The study did not consider print sales or access to content provided by any content aggregators unless they linked to the content on the SpringerLink platform. Clark & Hill (2020) present the results of a survey of nearly 5000 humanities and social science researchers by Cambridge University Press and Oxford University Press. It is clear from this research that monographs play a central role in enabling scholars to understand and approach the literature, because book authors synthesize relevant literature into an accessible package. This is important for making it possible for scholars to keep up with advancements in knowledge. The survey also revealed that readers often interact with monographs on a chapter level, where over 80% responded that they were at least very likely to browse chapter headings and read specific chapters. Less than 40% were very or extremely likely to read a monograph cover-to-cover. Concerning digital monographs, there was a split in reader views. One substantial part of the respondents wanted more advanced features so that books can become more dynamic, interactive, updatable, and interlinked. Another substantial part wanted digital versions to mimic print editions in having identical page numbering and illustrations. Affordability was a key obstacle for many readers.

OA books are succeeding in extending the reach of scholarly literature to new users (Watkinson, Welzenbach, Hellman et al 2017; Hellman 2019) based on interviews (with JSTOR, Project Muse, Bowker (part of ProQuest), EBSCO, and Yankee Book Peddler/Gobi Library Solutions (now owned by EBSCO)), web server logs, and Google Analytics data for a sample of books published by Open Book Publishers (OBP) and University of Michigan Press (UMP). A small number of titles were found to generate a large share of the access numbers. The study found that very little use of the books was coming from library systems. However, the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) was found to be a significant source of traffic. OA books were found to reach readers outside the academy, with social media and promotion within personal and professional networks were important for discovery. From the 17 user interviews conducted it was found that users of ebooks often move to print to read the whole volume rather than read through the entire content from an electronic device, that there was strong interest in use of the content for courses, and that users rarely curate downloaded copies.

There is a global readership even for books with a regional focus (Snijder 2022) with data indicating that in many countries the 10 most downloaded books are written in languages other than English. Even when English language titles are part of the top 10, many address regional concerns. The article counters the narrative of the dominance of English as the language of scholarly communication and supports the value of bibliodiversity.

Economics

Librarians are price and cost conscious, and this was a very major driver for the push to OA publishing for journals. This has often also expressed itself in requests for transparency about the costs of producing journals and journal articles.

Price and cost are of course also concerns with books, and therefore a key driver; however, it is not the only matter of concern. Librarians are also concerned about the licence under which an OA book is published, perpetual access to ebooks acquired under any revenue model, and of course meeting the needs of readers and authors on their campuses.

There are some other key differences between journals and books that mean the conversation around publishing economics is different. For example, articles tend to be unique and books (except for edited works or monographs) have competitors. Another difference is that editorial and quality assurance is done in-house by book editors, while journal publishers outsource this work to editorial board members. Lastly, journals primarily cater to an academic audience, whereas books are often read by a broader and more diverse readership.

There have been studies about the costs of producing books, and attempts to begin a discussion about what is reasonable or high or low (e.g. Maron, Schmelzinger, Mulhern et al 2016; Maron & Schmelzinger 2022). The concept of an average price for book publishing is, however, too simplistic because manuscripts differ widely in terms of editing required, length, illustrations and layout requirements, secondary rights clearance costs, etc. There is also interest in better understanding whether Book Processing Charges (BPCs) represent value for money.

Economics are also important for book publishers and they are keenly focused on the cost of doing business and how to recover those costs. Monographs have always had a more limited audience than journals, and so book publishers are accustomed to careful curation and planning. Publishers also need to be mindful of the needs of authors and readers. In an OAPEN study (Ferwerda et al. 2013) most of the book costs were first copy costs, and the next highest cost of production was 30% for the creation of print versions. If a publisher sought to reduce costs they could simply cut print; however, there are other reasons to have print editions, as these are important for authors and readers. Print also remains a significant medium for disseminating and consuming books and for generating book publishing revenue (Brown, Dayan, McLaughlin et al 2023). A number of studies suggest that the impact of having an OA version available digitally has minimal impact on print sales (Ferwerda, Snijder, Arpagaus et al 2018; Milloy & Collins 2016; Snijder 2014).

A Digital Monograph Costing Tool is available to enable publishers to calculate per-title costs (aupresses.org 2016), but infrastructure for calculating and sharing cost and price data is in its infancy for OA books.

Institutional expenditure

Money for OA book publishing is essential if there is to be a transition. For *journals* this money first became available when authors included requests for funding to cover APCs in their grants. The transition to OA increased when libraries and consortia shifted their spending from subscriptions to support OA through fully OA or transformative agreements.

It is early days for the OA book transition, but so far the pattern is different because there is relatively little funding from authors or libraries. Perhaps because of the importance of books in the HSS fields, relatively few authors appear to have funding available to pay for OA book publishing (Shaw, Phillips & Gutiérrez 2023). Libraries'

commitment to open research in principle is not necessarily reflected in their collection development approaches (Ball, Stone & Thompson 2021).

Libraries are often rewarded, and therefore motivated, to demonstrate that their purchased content is relevant to users, which can lead to behaviours that promote purchased collections over open content. Ball, Stone & Thompson (2021) call for libraries to be more mindful and for a collaborative international approach, cultural change, and leadership to establish open content as the norm. Policies, practices, and structures will all need to change.

There is some research on what OA initiatives libraries are most prepared to fund (e.g. Barnes, Welzenbach & Folger 2017). Content quality and relevance are essential, as is the availability, and sustainability, of library funding. Straightforward models, preferably with tiered or progressive pricing, that do not require extensive explanation to be understood and evaluated were seen as desirable, as was comprehensive usage data. Institutions expect a growth in OA book publishing, are concerned about the equity and sustainability of BPCs, and are interested in supporting other revenue models such as repository distribution and collaborative publishing services and consortial funding models (Roberts & Johnson 2024).

A summary of recent projects and their outcomes, summarized by several US academic library representatives, echoed this call for more, braver steps¹⁶:

'Whereas open access strategies have tended to consolidate commercial power in journal publishing, the late blooming of OA in monograph publishing offers an opportunity to sustain non-profit leadership. University libraries and presses play a pivotal role in shaping the future of academic publishing, and it is time for us to rally together, explore new pathways, and remove the barriers that hinder OA for monographs. This is a call to action — a call to open 25 university press frontlists by 2030.'

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science¹⁷ provides an international framework for open science policy and practice that aims to reduce the technological and knowledge divides between and within countries. The Recommendation outlines a common definition and shared values, principles and standards for open science at the international level, and it proposes actions to support fair and equitable open science for all, at individual, institutional, national, regional and international levels.

Library and new university presses

New publishing entrants, often distinguishing themselves from more established publishers by ideology and principles, are driving change (Crow 2012, Lockett & Speicher 2016, Adema & Stone 2017, Fradenburg Joy & van Gerven Oei 2023). There are now 81 members of the Library Publishing Coalition¹⁸ and 19 members of the Open Institutional Publishing Association¹⁹. The IFLA Library Publishing Special Interest Group provides a map of global library publishing initiatives²⁰. In Adema & Stone's (2017) survey among new university presses in the UK, common reasons for establishing a new press were to advance OA publishing and to enable publishing by more early career researchers and academics. Almost all of these presses are supported financially by their institution and staffed from within the libraries, and most do not charge APCs or BPCs.

¹⁶ <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2023/09/20/guest-post-open-access-to-university-press-frontlists-a-call-to-action/>

¹⁷ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about?hub=686>

¹⁸ <https://librarypublishing.org/about/>

¹⁹ <https://oipauk.org/membership/current-members/>

²⁰ <https://lib-pub.org/>

In general, the outputs are low in volume. In 2023, members of OIPA (all of which are UK university presses) published a total of 248 titles, of which 232 came from just three members (Liverpool, Edinburgh, and UCL University Presses). 65 of these titles were OA of some sort, with 48 being hybrid (these data are all taken from Dimensions and use Dimensions' definitions). A similar pattern is seen in the USA: excluding UCL, which belongs to both organizations, LPC members published 967 titles in 2023, mainly driven by Columbia, Rutgers, California, and Michigan (678 titles combined). 255 of these are listed as OA, again with a high proportion of hybrid book titles (179).

For further valuable insight into how these presses function and perceive the environment we recommend 'Mapping the Publishing Challenges for an Open Access University Press' (Taylor 2019).

Academics also engage in establishing new university presses, and punctum books provides an interesting illustration. Founded in 2011 without any backing organization or funding, the California-based press ran for many years purely on the motivation, drive, and personal savings of a few dedicated people (Adema & Stone 2017). It is clear that money has not been a primary motivator. Rather, the driver is an ideological mission to fill an important gap in the scholarly communication landscape (Fradenburg Joy & van Gerven Oei 2023):

'We believe that the business model of any non-profit scholarly publisher is not a 'problem' to be solved apart from or to the side of the editorial mission and its public goods, but must be rooted in and extend from the mission. ...we need a business model that is not just about 'How can we keep making OA books and pay ourselves and our staff?' but more importantly is about 'How can we keep making OA books in ways that attend to bibliodiversity as well as to the affective care of ourselves, our authors, and the institutions that fund us?' At the same time that we want to see a tighter, more symbiotic relationship between any scholarly publisher's mission and business model, it is important to not let the business side of things overdetermine an editorial mission. It should actually be the other way around. ...our primary mission now is to have a successful business model that enables and is scaled to our mission and values, and to do it with the support of libraries that share our vision for bibliodiversity, the ethics of care, and the responsible co-stewardship of public funds.'

A similar core ideology can be perceived throughout the COPIM project²¹. Amongst its many outputs are recommendations for how to set up a sustainable governance structure that ensures editorial independence, diverse participation, and sustainable financing without the threat of a commercial buyout (Hart, Adema & COPIM 2022). The COPIM project also developed two highly influential collective funding models: Opening the Future (Eve, Pinter, Poznanski et al 2022), and The Open Book Collective²², which share the concept of streamlining the process for both libraries and publishers. Publishers gain visibility, awareness, and financial support through a distributed network of supporters. Libraries gain the ability to select the publishers and book collections they want to support through a central platform.

There are of course many OA book publishers outside the UK and US, with active academic publishers in most, if not all, European countries. A recent review suggests that many publishers do not yet have clearly articulated OA publishing options or policies for their authors (PALOMERA Project, forthcoming). This point is of course of relevance to all publishers embracing OA models for books.

²¹ <https://www.copim.ac.uk/>

²² <https://openbookcollective.org/>

It is not uncommon for publishers to provide short descriptions of their individual models (e.g. Newton, Dacos & Mounier et al 2014; openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org), which are valuable sources of inspiration for experimentation among other publishers. What is already a valuable resource for tracking what is going on, and will continue to be so in the future, is the OA book business model page of The Open Access Directory²³. The directory maintains a list of OA book business and revenue models, describes their core characteristics, and provides examples of publishers that have used each of the models.

Infrastructure and shared services

The 2019 report 'The State of Open Monographs' by Grimme et al. (2019) provides a helpful review of the historical and technical origins which explain why the data landscape for OA books is so fragmented, highlighting in particular the complexity introduced by the sprawling practices for how DOIs, ISBNs, MARC, and ONIX are implemented for OA book content across publishers.

The OAPEN library and the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) have become important services in which metadata of published content is stored and used for various discovery and indexing services which make use of the standardized metadata curated in these services. Both services have over a decade of history behind them which has involved substantial changes to their funding, governance and technical features. Ferwerda, Snijder & Stern (2023) summarize the history and current status of the services, highlighting the emphasis on making OA book content as discoverable as possible regardless of the services that potential readers use to look for content.

Perhaps unsurprisingly, given the confluence of funder policy and institutional practice, shared infrastructure for OA book publishing has emerged, although there are still significant gaps and the infrastructure is not yet joined (Ferwerda, Mosterd, Snijder, et al 2021). During the last decade, there have been several national and European projects that have built infrastructure for OA books. Stern (2021) provides a helpful narrative for the origins of OPERAS (open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities) and how many of the related initiatives like OAPEN (Open Access Publishing in European Networks), DOAB, and OpenEdition are connected in this context.

OAPEN started out as a project funded by the European Commission and became a legal non-profit Dutch entity in 2011. The OAPEN Library hosts, disseminates, and facilitates the preservation of OA books. The OAPEN Foundation launched the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) in 2012, inspired and supported by DOAJ. It indexes and provides access to scholarly, peer-reviewed OA books. DOAB became a legal non-profit Dutch entity in 2019, managed by the OAPEN Foundation and OpenEdition. The OAPEN Foundation also manages the OAPEN Open Access Toolkit, which aims to help book authors to better understand OA book publishing and to increase trust in OA books.

In some cases the OA infrastructure built for journals is being used to cover books, but is not yet widespread. For example, OpenAPC has been set up to track expenditure on journal APCs and is used by over 400 contributing institutions around the world. As of May 2024 only 61 institutions have contributed BPC data for books.

It is clear that OA infrastructure for books still lags behind that available for journals, particularly when it comes to library workflows. For example, a key initiative that has facilitated library uptake of OA models for journals is the Efficiency and Standards for Article Charges (ESAC) Registry. There is no book equivalent, possibly because library

²³ https://oad.simmons.edu/oadwiki/OA_book_business_models

budgets have not yet transitioned to prioritize OA book acquisition and promotions. The transition of library budgets is stymied because the book supply chain and workflows do not always properly support OA.

Established publishers

The transition of journals to OA was not lost on book publishers, and it is unsurprising that the voluntary efforts of established publishers have also been a driver toward OA book publishing (e.g. Shaw, Phillips & Gutiérrez 2023).

The UK is unique when it comes to its book publishing landscape (Ferwerda et al. 2017). Around two thirds of monographs in the social sciences and humanities are published by UK publishers Routledge (an imprint of Taylor & Francis), OUP, CUP, and Palgrave (an imprint of SpringerNature).

There have been productive collaborations between funders and publishing industry associations in the UK. For example, in 2019 the Wellcome Trust, UKRI, and the Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers commissioned a project to support society publishers to accelerate their transition to OA in alignment with Plan S (Wise & Estelle 2020). This Society Publishers Accelerating Open Access and Plan S (SPA OPS) project, was initially focused on journals and now, in its fourth phase (i.e. this report), is focused on books.

In a recent study focusing on changes in the UK learned society landscape specifically, Johnson & Malcolmson (2024) observed the trajectories of 277 societies over the years 2015-2023. While the study was focussed primarily on journal publishing the results also provide context to better understand the overall evolution of society publishing activities. The results suggest a rapid decline in the number of self-published societies, an increased reliance on larger publisher partners, and a decline in revenue from publishing. An obvious implication of more learned societies being published through commercial partners means that their OA options are more likely to be governed by those partners. This might open up options that will help OA book publishing to scale up and/or it might restrict access to alternative options not favoured by the partner.

It is important to keep in mind that countries outside the UK have different traditions and practices related to book publication, and can present surprises for UK-based authors when collaborating with authors from different countries. In the UK it has not been common practice to have author-side fees in conjunction with book publication. However, Feenstra and López-Cózar (2022) describe how it is a relatively normal practice for academic book publications with national book publishers to involve author payments even though the books are not published OA. The fees, which only rarely exceed €3000, are to ensure the financial viability of publishers for their work with content that does not have high commercial potential. The COPIM project in collaboration with OPERAS-P has produced short overview articles covering the OA book publishing landscapes in 14 European countries that illustrate this diverse landscape (Morka and Gatti 2021).

In his description of how and why the publication landscapes between STEM and the AHSS differ so much, Mounier (2018) suggests that there has not been the same consolidation pattern in the landscape as for STEM because 'The diversity of publication venues reflects the epistemic diversity of social sciences and humanities (SSH) communities.'

References

Adema, J., Stone, G. (2017). Changing Publishing Ecologies—A Landscape Study of New University Presses and Academic-Led Publishing.

<https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6666/1/Changing-publishing-ecologies-report.pdf>

Adema, J. (2019). *Towards a Roadmap for Open Access Monographs: A Knowledge Exchange Report*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.2644997>

Anderson, R. (2023). The Open Access Fund at Edinburgh University Press: An Interview with Nicola Ramsey. The Scholarly Kitchen.

<https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2023/09/11/the-open-access-fund-at-edinburgh-university-press-an-interview-with-nicola-ramsey/>. Accessed 7th of June 2024.

aupresses.org (2016). Digital Monograph Costing Tool.

<https://aupresses.org/resources/costing-tool/>.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20240501214554/https://aupresses.org/resources/costing-tool/>. Accessed 1 May 2024.

Ball, J., Stone, G., & Thompson, S. (2021). Opening up the Library: Transforming our Policies, Practices and Structures. *LIBER Quarterly: The Journal of the Association of European Research Libraries*, 31(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.18352/lq.10360>

Barnes, M., Cole, G., Fry, J., Gatti, R., & Higman, R. (2023). 'Good, Better, Best': Practices in Archiving & Preserving Open Access Monographs (Version 1.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7876048>

Barnes & Van Schalkwyk (2022). Business Models for Open Access Books

<https://oabooksbusinessmodels.pubpub.org/>. Accessed 7 June 2024.

Barnes, C., Welzenbach, R., & Folger, K. (2017). *Surveying the Scalability of Open Access Monograph Initiatives: Final Report*.

<https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/handle/2027.42/139888?show=full>

bigtenopenbooks.org (2024). Big Ten Open Books. <https://bigtenopenbooks.org/>. Accessed 7 June 2024.

Brown, L., Dayan, M., McLaughlin, B., Schonfeld, R. C., Sherer, J., & van Rijn, E. (2023, September 19). Print Revenue and Open Access Monographs: A University Press Study.

<https://doi.org/10.18665/sr.319642>

Braak, P., De Jonge, H., Trentacosti, G., Verhagen, I., & Woutersen-Windhower, S. (2020). Guide to Creative Commons for Scholarly Publications and Educational Resources (Version final). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4090922>

Brundy, C., Hanscom, L., Kern, B., and Weinstein, B. (2023). Open Access to University Press Frontlists: A Call to Action. Scholarly Kitchen.

<https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2023/09/20/guest-post-open-access-to-university-press-frontlists-a-call-to-action/>. Accessed 16 July 2024.

Clark, D., & Hill, M. (2020). Researchers' Perspectives on the Purpose and Value of the Monograph. *Commonplace*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/6ffd8432.6489b1ba>

Clarke, M. and Ricci, L. (2021). *OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report*.

<https://zenodo.org/records/4681725>.

Collins, E., Milloy, C., & Stone, G. (2015). *Guide to open access monograph publishing for arts, humanities and social science researchers*. Jisc Collections.

<https://eprints.hud.ac.uk/25391/>

Crossick, G. (2015). Monographs and open access. A report to HEFCE.

<http://www.hefce.ac.uk/pubs/rereports/year/2015/monographs/>

Crossick, G. (2016) 'Monographs and Open Access', *Insights: the UKSG journal*, 29(1), p. 14-19. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.280>

Crotty, D (2024) Variability, Irregular Publisher Metadata, and the Ongoing Evolution of Databases Complicates Reproducibility in Bibliometrics Research. The Scholarly Kitchen. <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2024/08/15/variability-bad-publisher-metadata-and-the-ongoing-evolution-of-databases-makes-bibliometrics-research-reproducibility-difficult>

Crow, R. (2012). *A Rational System for Funding Scholarly Monographs: A White Paper Prepared for the AAU-ARL Task Force on Scholarly Communication*. <https://www.arl.org/resources/a-rational-system-for-funding-scholarly-monographs/>

Eve, M. P., Pinter, F., Poznanski, E., & Grady, T. (2022). Opening the Future: How to Implement an Equitable Revenue Model for Open Access Monographs (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7003979>

Farrell, E., Poznanski, E., and Watkinson, C. (2021), Building a Framework Together for Assessing OA Book Publishing Models. *Commonplace*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.21428/6ffd8432.185d3532>

Feenstra, R.A. and López-Cózar, E.D. (2022), Philosophers' perceptions of pay to publish and open access in Spain: Books versus journals, more than a financial dilemma. *Learned Publishing*, 35: 118-129. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1426>

Ferwerda, E., Mosterd, T., Snijder, R., & Mounier, P. (2021). UKRI Gap Analysis of Open Access Monographs Infrastructure. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5771945org/10.3998/jep.3627>

Ferwerda, E., Pinter, F., & Stern, N. (2017). *A Landscape Study on Open Access and Monographs: Policies, Funding and Publishing in Eight European Countries* (p. 184). Knowledge Exchange. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.815932>

Ferwerda, E., Snijder, R., Adema, J. (2013). OAPEN-NL – A project exploring Open Access monograph publishing in the Netherlands : Final Report.

Ferwerda, E., Snijder, R., Arpagaus, B., Graf, R., Krämer, D., & Moser, E. (2018). OAPEN-CH – The impact of open access on scientific monographs in Switzerland. A project conducted by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1220607>

Ferwerda, E., Snijder, R. & Stern, N., (2023) 'Open Access to Books – the Perspective of a Non-profit Infrastructure Provider', *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 26(1). Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.3303>

Fradenburg Joy, E. A. & van Gerven Oei, V. W., (2023) 'What is Your Threshold? The Economics of Open Access Scholarly Book Publishing, the 'Business' of Care, and the Case of punctum books', *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 26(1). Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.3627>.

Frankl, J., (2023) 'Towards an Author-Centered Open Access Monograph Program: Understanding Open Access Cultures in Scholarly Publishing', *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 26(1). Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.3332>

Grimme, S., Taylor, M., Elliott, M. A., Holland, C., Potter, P., & Watkinson, C. (2019). *The State of Open Monographs: An analysis of the Open Access monograph landscape and its integration into the digital scholarly network*. Digital Science. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.8197625.v4>

Grove, J. (2024). UK learned societies blast REF open access proposals for books. Times Higher Education, June 18 2024. <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/news/uk-learned-societies-blast-ref-open-access-proposals-books>

Hart, P., Adema, J., & COPIM. (2022). Towards Better Practices for the Community Governance of Open Infrastructures (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6535460>

Hellman, E. S. (2019). *The Open-Factor: Toward impact-aligned measures of open-access ebook usage*. Journal of Electronic Publishing 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0022.104>

Hunt, M., & Picarra, M. (2016). Open Access Policy Alignment. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.51862>

Jackson, R. (2014). The publisher journey for OUP. *Insights: The UKSG Journal*, 27(s1), Article s1. <https://doi.org/10.1629/2048-7754.117>

Johnson, R., & Malcolmson, E. (2024). You don't know what you've got till it's gone: The changing landscape of UK learned society publishing. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10933141>

JSTOR (2024). Path to Open. <https://www.about.jstor.org/path-to-open/>. Accessed 7th of June 2024

Laakso, M. (2023). Open access books through open data sources: Assessing prevalence, providers, and preservation. Journal of Documentation 79, no. 7 (June). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-02-2023-0016>

Lockett, A. and Speicher, L. (2016), New university presses in the UK: Accessing a mission. *Learned Publishing*, 29: 320-329. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1049>
longleafservices.org (n.d). The Sustainable History Monograph Pilot. <https://longleafservices.org/the-sustainable-history-monograph-pilot/>. Accessed 18th of June 2024

Marques, M., & Stone, G. (2020). Transitioning to Open Access: An Evaluation of the UK Springer Compact Agreement Pilot 2016–2018. *College & Research Libraries*, 81(6), 913–927. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.81.6.913>

Maron, N., Schmelzinger, K., Mulhern, C., & Rossman, D. (2016). The Costs of Publishing Monographs: Toward a Transparent Methodology. *The Journal of Electronic Publishing*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0019.103>

Maron, Nancy L., and Kimberly Schmelzinger. (2022). The Cost to Publish TOME Monographs: A Preliminary Report. New York: Association of University Presses. <https://doi.org/10.17613/pvek-7q97>

Mellins-Cohen, T. (2024) . Classifying Open Access business models. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/11242106>

Milloy, C., Collins, E. (2016). OAPEN-UK final report: A five-year study into open access monograph publishing in the humanities and social sciences.

Montgomery, L. (2014). Knowledge Unlatched: A Global Library Consortium Model for Funding Open Access Scholarly Books. *Cultural Science*, 7(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.5334/csci.68>

Mounier, P. (2018). 'Publication favela' or bibliodiversity? Open access publishing viewed from a European perspective. *Learned Publishing* 31, no. S1 (September): 299-305. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1194>

Morka, A., & Gatti, R. (2021). Academic Libraries and Open Access Books in Europe. A Landscape Study. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4483773>

National Acquisitions Group & Southern Universities Purchasing Consortium. (2021). Metadata Profiles: MARC21 Records for Print and Electronic Books. <https://www.nag.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/NAG-SUPC-Metadata-Profiles-MARC21-Records-for-Print-Electronic-Books-v2.pdf>

Nature, S., Pyne, R., Emery, C., Lucraft, M., & Pinck, A. S. (2019). The future of open access books: Findings from a global survey of academic book authors. figshare. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.8166599.v1>

Neylon, C., Ozaygen, A., Montgomery, L., Huang, C.-K. (Karl), Pyne, R., Lucraft, M., & Emery, C. (2021). More readers in more places: The benefits of open access for scholarly books. *Insights: The UKSG Journal*, 34(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.558>

Newton, H., Dacos, M., Mounier, P., & Neuman, Y. (2014). Snapshots of three open access business models. *Insights: The UKSG Journal*, 27(s1), Article s1. <https://doi.org/10.1629/2048-7754.118>

The Open Access Books Toolkit (2023). Business models for open access book publishing <https://www.oabooks-toolkit.org/lifecycle/10944589-planning-funding/article/10432084-business-models-for-open-access-book-publishing>. Accessed June 7th 2024

GitHub (2024) OpenAPC project page. <https://github.com/OpenAPC/openapc-de> (Accessed 17th of June 2024)

openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org (2024). Open Access Book Network – Publisher Spotlight. <https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/category/publisher-spotlight/>. Accessed 1st of July 2024

Penier, I., Eve, M. P., & Grady, T. (2020). *COPIM – Revenue Models for Open Access Monographs 2020* (v2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4455511>

Pinter, F. (2018). Why Book Processing Charges (BPCs) Vary So Much. *Journal of Electronic Publishing*, 21(1), Article 1. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0021.101>

Roberts, A. & Johnson, R. (2024) Open Access book publishing in a challenging funding landscape. Research Consulting Blog. <https://www.research-consulting.com/open-access-book-publishing-in-a-challenging-funding-landscape/#OpenAccess>. Accessed 7th of June 2024

Rubow, L., Schofield, B., & Shen, R. (2018). Understanding Open Access: When, Why & How to Make Your Work Openly Accessible. Project Muse, Samuelson Law, Technology, and Public Policy Clinic. <https://authorsalliance.org/wp-content/uploads/Documents/Guides/Authors%20Alliance%20-%20Understanding%20Open%20Access.pdf>

Science Europe Briefing Paper On Open Access to Academic Books. (2019). <http://scieur.org/oa-books>

Shaw, P., Phillips, A., & Gutiérrez, M. B. (2023). The Future of the Monograph in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences: Publisher Perspectives on a Transitioning Format. *Publishing Research Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12109-023-09937-1>

Sherer, J. (2023). Guest Post — Open Access for Monographs is Here. But Are we Ready for It?. The Scholarly Kitchen. March 23 2023. <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2023/03/23/guest-post-open-access-for-monographs-is-here-but-are-we-ready-for-it/>

Snijder, R. (2014). The Influence of Open Access on Monograph Sales : The experience at Amsterdam University Press. LOGOS: The Journal of the World Book Community, 25(3), 13–23. <https://doi.org/10.1163/1878-4712-11112047>

Snijder, R. (2015). Better Sharing Through Licenses? Measuring the Influence of Creative Commons Licenses on the Usage of Open Access Monographs. *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication*, 3(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1187>

Snijder, R. (2021). Open access book usage data – how close is COUNTER to the other kind? Insights: the UKSG Journal, 34(1), 9. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.539>

Snijder, R. (2022). Big in Japan, Zimbabwe or Brazil – global reach and national preferences for open access books. Insights: the UKSG Journal 35(11). <https://insights.uksg.org/articles/10.1629/uksg.580>

Snijder, R. (2023). Measured in a context: making sense of open access book data. *Insights: The UKSG Journal*, 36(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.627>

Snyder, L. O. & Fathallah, J., (2023) 'Sustainable Futures for OA Books: The Open Book Collective', *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 26(1). <https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.3372>

Speicher L., Armando, L., Bargheer, M. Paul Eve, M., Fund, S., Leão, D., Mosterd, M., Pinter, F., & Souyioultzoglou, I. (2018). OPERAS Open Access Business Models White Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1323708>

Suber, P. (2017). Why Is Open Access Moving So Slowly In The Humanities? The Blog of the American Philosophical Association (APA) <https://blog.apaonline.org/2017/06/08/open-access-in-the-humanities-part-2/> (Accessed on 29 June 2024)

Taylor, M. (2019). Mapping the Publishing Challenges for an Open Access University Press. *Publications*, 7(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7040063>

Universities UK Open Access Monographs Group. (2019). *Open access and monographs: Evidence review*. Universities UK, Open Access and monographs group. <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/34475>

Watkinson, C., Welzenbach, R., Hellman, E. , Gatti, R. & Sonnenberg, K. (2017). *Mapping Free Ebook Supply Chain—Final Report to the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation*. https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/bitstream/handle/2027.42/137638/Mapping%2520Free%2520Ebook%2520Supply%2520Chain_Final%2520Report.pdf%3Fsequence%3D1&ved=2ahUKEwiJ9sDPuJGFaxVKExAIHWNsBB8QFnoECBMQAQ&usq=AOvVaw1gZTYDAk7e_BIzOyRGekrC

Wise, A., Estelle, L. (2020). How society publishers can accelerate their transition to open access and align with Plan S. *Learned Publishing*, 33: 14-27. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1272>

Zhang, M., & Eschenfelder, K. (2023). The relationship between university presses, e-book vendors, and academic libraries: A platform theory analysis. *Journal of*

Librarianship and Information Science, 0(0).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/09610006231185883>